

VALUE4FARM

D2.4 Crop protocol for the Mediterranean region

Start date of the project:	01/09/2023
Duration of the project:	42 months
Deliverable n° & name	D2.4 Crop protocol for the Mediterranean region
Version:	1
Work-package n°:	2
Due date of D:	M9, 31/05/2024
Actual date of D:	30/05/2024
Participant responsible:	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
Main authors:	Stefano Amaducci
Project website address:	www.value4farm.eu

Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open and automatically posted online	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grand Agreement	
CI	Classified information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
	Classified information: CONFIDENTIAL UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
	Classified information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	

Quality procedure			
Date	Version	Reviewers	Comments
07/05/2024	V1	Sander Vandendriessche (INA), Esperanza Huerta Lwanga (WUR)	General comment on structure and typos
	V2		

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Alternating Current
AGB	Above ground Biomass
APV	Agrivoltaics
AVS	Agrivoltaics systems
BBCH	Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt and Chemical industry
BDR	BiogasDoneRight
CCI	Chlorophyll Concentration Index
CFT	Cool Farm Tool
CIB	Consorzio Italiano Biogas
COS	Characteristic Operating Space
DC	Direct Current
FL	Full Light
GCR	Ground Cover Ratio
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LMA	Leaf Mass Area
LUE	Light Use Efficiency
NPQ	Non-photochemical quenching
NUE	Nitrogen Use Efficiency
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
PVP	Photovoltaic panels
REM	RemTec srl
ROS	Reactive Oxygen species
SLA	Specific Leaf Area

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure 1. Photosynthetic response curve to light intensity, showing light compensation and saturation points (Benedetti et al., 2018).</u>	13
<u>Figure 3 Top view of the agrivoltaic plant at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC).</u>	17
<u>Figure 4 Technology 1.0 installed in Virgilio (Mantova, Italy)</u>	18
<u>Figure 4. Watch-Dog weather station (left), Delta-T weather station (right).</u>	26
<u>Figure 5. Shade-depth map obtained in the study by Potenza et al. (2022). The experimental area was divided into four cultivation zones. For each of them, a shade-dept value was estimated with the simulation platform described in Amaducci et al. (2018).</u>	27
<u>Figure 6. Map of the global radiation ($W m^{-2}$) variability of the agri-voltaic plant at UCSC generated by the UCSC simulation platform</u>	28
<u>Figure 7. Monthly average ‘Shade depth’, 15 m pitch area. Resolution 0.2 m at UCSC</u>	29
<u>Figure 8. Absolute mean percentage difference (%) and relative standard error (%) with increasing number of sampling points</u>	30
<u>Figure 9. Maize experimental design depicting sowing densities (left) and shading depth treatments (right). Sowing densities: D12 = 12 plants m^{-2}, D8 = 8 plants m^{-2}, D6 = 6 plants m^{-2}. Shading depth treatments (from left to right): AV5 = 29.5%, AV4 = 23.1%, AV3 = 16.1%, AV2 = 15.3%, AV1 = 22.0%.</u>	35
<u>Figure 10. Schematic representation of the experimental design for potato crop in APV.</u>	38
<u>Figure 12 crop rotation tested in the BDR protocol</u>	44
<u>Figure 13 Monitoring and verification workflow</u>	46
<u>Figure 14 Ideal pathways for farms to enter the characteristic operating space, based on yield-N input relationships and sustainable intensification strategies (source: Quemada et al., 2020).</u>	48

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Main parameters collected under agrivoltaic condition. Crop (C), Agronomic (A), Photovoltaic (P), Soil (S) and Micrometeorological (M) parameters.....	19
Table 2. Pre harvest Measurements for wheat crop under APV. Each sub-plot stands for a different light treatment, or shading depth.	32
Table 3. Post harvest measurements. From randomly selected plant samples for each sub-plot, the following measurements are taken once, after harvest or just before.	33
Table 4. Pre harvest Measurements for Maize crop under APV. Each sub-plot stands for a different light treatment, or shading depth.	35
Table 5. Post harvest measurements. From randomly selected plant samples for each sub-plot, the following measurements are taken once.	36
Table 6. Pre harvest Measurements for potato crop under APV.	38
Table 7. Post harvest measurements for potato.	39
Table 8. Overview of environmental parameters required for parameterisation of crop models Daisy and Gecros.	40
Table 9. Information required for calibration of phenology.	41
Table 10. Parameters relevant to simulate growth.....	41

Value4Farm

KEYWORDS LIST

Agrivoltaics; Biomethane; Maize; Winter wheat; Potato

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101116076. This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained there in.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of abbreviations	3
List of figures.....	4
List of tables.....	5
Keywords list.....	6
Table of contents	7
Executive summary.....	9
1. Introduction.....	10
2. Study plant response to agrivoltaic conditions.....	12
2.1. Crop models for Agrivoltaics	15
2.2. Agrivoltaic plant	16
2.2.1. @UCSC.....	16
2.2.2. @REM.....	17
2.3. Objectives of the experimental trials: general aspects	18
3. Monitoring of agrivoltaic conditions	19
3.1. Crop measurements in agrivoltaic conditions.....	19
3.1.1. Crop phenology	21
3.1.2. Crop height	22
3.1.3. Leaf Area Index (LAI).....	22
3.1.4. Specific Leaf Area.....	23
3.1.5. SPAD Chlorophyll Content.....	24
3.1.6. Yield and yield components	24
3.2. Defining the optimal number of area for monitoring agrivoltaic conditions.....	26
3.3. Crop-specific protocols	31
3.3.1. Winter wheat.....	31
3.3.2. Maize.....	34
3.3.3. Potato	37
3.4. Crop models parameterisation.....	40
4. BiogasDoneRight® protocols	43
4.1. Objectives of the experimental trials	43
4.2. Description of experimental trials.....	43

4.3.	Monitoring and Verification of <i>Biogasdoneright</i> protocols impacts at field level	45
4.4.	Scenario analyses of BDR protocol adoption at farm level	47
5.	Conclusion	49
6.	References	50

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Value4Farm (V4F) project is exploring the synergy between agrivoltaic (APV) and biomethane technologies. It focuses on using APV-generated electricity to power biomethane plants and growing APV systems with both cash crops and crops suitable for conversion to biogas. Building on the foundations laid in deliverables D1.1 (Collection of farmers' needs) and D1.2 (Demonstration sites' specifications and requirements), the project will explore practical applications of this innovative concept while conducting Italian demonstration sites.

In Italy, the V4F project partners, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) and REM Tec (REM), will demonstrate the optimal combination of crops with horizontal agrivoltaics, as illustrated in deliverable D1.2. UCSC and REM are collaborating with the Italian Biogas Consortium (CIB) to integrate agrivoltaics with biomethane production, with the goal of creating an efficient, fully off-grid biomethane plant powered by 100 percent renewable energy.

The research is investigating the conditions under which farm-scale APV systems can provide off-grid power to biomethane plants while still growing cash crops. The scalability of APV systems to increase renewable energy production without sacrificing food/feed and biomethane production potential is also being evaluated. Experimental data are being used to calibrate and validate an APV simulation platform, which will optimize the design and operation of APV plants.

In addition, the project is implementing the BiogasDoneRight® initiative, evaluating crop rotations that include winter cover crops and nitrogen-fixing plants to improve soil fertility and food/feed production. This builds on insights gained from focus group discussions in deliverable D1.1, ensuring that the identified main crop is included in the crop rotation.

The APV systems studied in the project will be comprehensively monitored by collecting a wide range of crop and micro-meteorological parameters through sensors, sampling, and observations. This includes input variables, such as manure and fertiliser inputs and mechanical cultivation practices, as well as output variables, such as crop yield, productivity, efficiency, quality, and electrical performance of APVs.

The experimental trials are studying the response of various crops to APV shading conditions, including cash crops (potatoes, tomatoes, aromatic crops), food and industrial crops (soybean and hemp), and crops for biomethane production (corn, sorghum, wheat). The data collected will be used to calibrate and validate crop models, define agronomic protocols for growing APVs, and evaluate strategies for integrating APVs and biomethane production. Two strategies were analysed: growing cash crops in small-scale APVs coupled with biomethane plants and implementing crop rotations for biomethane production in larger APV systems to produce electricity for both the biomethane plant and the grid.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agrioltaics (APV) emerged as a solution to the growing concern over land-use competition between energy production and agriculture. By integrating photovoltaic (PV) panels into agricultural fields, APV systems enable the dual use of land for both electricity generation and crop cultivation (Dupraz et al., 2011; Trommsdorff et al., 2021). This innovative approach is particularly relevant in regions facing the adverse effects of climate change, as the partial shading provided by PV panels can mitigate heat stress, reduce water evaporation, and protect crops from extreme weather events, ultimately leading to improved yields and resource efficiency.

Biomethane production, on the other hand, offers a sustainable and renewable energy source derived from organic waste, such as agricultural residues and animal manure. This versatile biogas can be upgraded to biomethane, a renewable natural gas equivalent that can be used for heating, electricity generation, and as a vehicle fuel. By utilizing waste streams and reducing reliance on fossil fuels, biomethane production contributes to a circular economy and helps mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.

The concept of agrioltaics dates back to the early 1980s, but its adoption in Europe has gained significant momentum in recent years, driven by supportive policies and technological advancements. While the exact land area covered by APV systems in Europe is not centrally tracked, numerous projects have been implemented across various countries, including Germany, France, Italy, and the Netherlands. Increasing the adoption of APV is crucial for several reasons: it can enhance land-use efficiency, improve agricultural resilience to climate change, and contribute to the transition towards renewable energy sources.

A wide variety of crops have been successfully cultivated under APV systems, including vegetables (e.g., lettuce, tomatoes, peppers), berries (e.g., strawberries, raspberries), and even field crops like wheat and soybeans. The choice of crops often depends on the specific APV system design and the local climatic conditions. For instance, shade-tolerant crops like lettuce and leafy greens may thrive under overhead APV systems, while taller crops like corn or sunflowers may be more suitable for interspaced APV systems. Research is ongoing to identify optimal crop combinations and cultivation practices for different APV configurations.

Within the Value4Farm project, research will delve deeper into the synergistic potential of APV and biomethane technologies. This involves investigating how electricity generated by APV systems can power biomethane plants, reducing their reliance on grid electricity or fossil fuels. Additionally, the project will explore the cultivation of both cash crops (e.g., processing tomatoes, potato) and energy crops (e.g., sorghum, maize) under APV systems. By integrating these two aspects, the project aims to demonstrate a holistic approach to sustainable agriculture and renewable energy generation.

The project will also evaluate the scalability of APV plants to increase renewable energy production while maintaining or even enhancing food/feed and biomethane production potential. This is crucial for ensuring the economic viability and long-term sustainability of APV systems. The data collected from these

experiments will be used to calibrate and validate an APV simulation platform developed by UCSC, which will help optimize the design and management of APV plants for different crops and climatic conditions.

The Value4Farm project will also leverage the expertise and resources of the Consorzio Italiano Biogas (CIB), a leading organization in the biogas sector. CIB's BiogasDoneRight® and FarmingForFuture initiatives promote sustainable agricultural practices and the integration of biogas production into farming systems. These initiatives align with the project's goals of improving soil fertility, enhancing food and feed production, and promoting using renewable energy sources in agriculture. By incorporating these initiatives, the Value4Farm project aims to demonstrate a comprehensive and integrated approach to sustainable farming and renewable energy generation.

Research activities carried out in WP3 will: i) demonstrate under which conditions farm-scale agrivoltaic technologies, cultivated with cash crops (e.g. processing tomatoes, potato), could off-grid bio-methane plants (REM); ii) evaluate the scaling-up of agrivoltaic (APV) plants on medium/large scale (> 20 ha) to increase the farm's renewable energy production, while maintaining its food/feed and biomethane production potential (UCSC). The data collected during the experimentation will be used to calibrate the APV simulation platform developed at UCSC and validate its accuracy. The platform will be used to optimise the design and management of APV plants, with dual-crop systems as proposed by CIB within the framework of BiogasDoneRight®.

During the project, several actions of the CIB's flagship initiative FarmingForFuture will be considered. This was to meet the needs highlighted by the focus groups conducted in WP1 (D1.1). This will be done through:

- i) the addition of winter cover crops to the crop rotation, which can be harvested before or after traditional food and feed crops, thus keeping the hectares devoted to food and feed almost at the same level as before, and producing a double harvest at the time of year when the land is set aside;
- ii) the introduction of nitrogen-fixing plants, such as fodder legumes, in rotation with other cereals for market and anaerobic digestion.

2. STUDY PLANT RESPONSE TO AGRIVOLTAIC CONDITIONS

Photosynthesis, the process by which plants convert sunlight, carbon dioxide (CO₂), and water into organic compounds, plays a crucial role in crop production. The maximum theoretical conversion efficiency of solar energy into biomass achieved through photosynthesis is approximately 4.6% for C3 plant species at 30°C and an atmospheric CO₂ concentration of 380 ppm. C4 plants, which represent a smaller subset of cultivated crops, can potentially reach efficiencies of up to 6% (Zhu et al., 2008).

The efficiency of photosynthesis is further limited by the plant's ability to utilize light. Photosynthetic rates increase with light intensity up to a saturation point (Figure 1), beyond which further increases can lead to photoinhibition (Benedetti et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2022). This phenomenon, caused by excessive light exposure, triggers the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that damage the photosynthetic apparatus and hinder biomass production. Crops particularly susceptible to photoinhibition include rice, wheat, and soybeans. These highly reactive molecules can damage the plant's photosynthetic apparatus, ultimately hindering biomass production (Benedetti et al., 2018; Peers et al., 2009; Tripathy and Oelmüller, 2012). Within certain limits, plants possess a protective mechanism known as non-photochemical quenching (NPQ). This process helps dissipate excess light energy as heat, thereby mitigating the formation of ROS and preventing photoinhibition damage (Benedetti et al., 2018). The effectiveness of NPQ varies depending on the plant species and even among different varieties within the same species. Importantly, some crops can adapt well to, or even benefit from, a reduction in PAR. This is particularly true for crops grown in regions with high levels of natural solar radiation, such as the Mediterranean region. By strategically designing APV systems to manage light transmittance and create targeted shading patterns, we can potentially leverage the natural tolerance of certain crops to lower light levels. This approach can contribute to optimizing crop health and yield within APV environments.

Figure 1. Photosynthetic response curve to light intensity, showing light compensation and saturation points (Benedetti et al., 2018).

Crop selection for APV systems is a complex process influenced by several factors including:

- Environmental conditions: Local climate, temperature, and sunlight intensity all play a role in determining crop suitability for APVs.
- Cultivation practices: Existing agricultural practices and crop management techniques need to be adapted or optimized for the unique microclimate created by APV systems.
- APV design and management characteristics: The design and management of the APV system itself, such as panel layout, spacing, and orientation, significantly influence the light and shade patterns experienced by crops.

Unfortunately, current knowledge is not yet sufficient to classify the suitability of every crop for the specific radiative and microclimatic conditions within APVs. Developing reliable simulation tools to predict the response of different crops to APV conditions would be a key element to sustain the development of commercially viable agricultural production systems. Modelling tools could then inform the design and management strategies for optimizing APV systems for specific crops. Laub et al. (2022) conducted a meta-analysis of 58 studies on crop response to shading. The analysis produced curves relating crop productivity ($t\ ha^{-1}$) to increasing shade levels (percentage reduction in solar radiation). By comparing the yield of shaded crops to those in full sun, the authors divided agricultural crops into three groups: crops that can benefit from shading, crops that tolerate shading and show an acceptable yield decline; crops that show high yield losses even with a slight level of shading. The results obtained from the analysis of

the studies considered suggest that the response to shading is not linear. For example, while maize and grain legumes react strongly to PAR reduction, several other types of crops may tolerate low levels of shading without showing appreciable yield reductions. In other crops, yield losses increase more than proportionally from irradiance reductions greater than 10%. This behaviour is typical of maize and C3 cereals (e.g., wheat, barley, oats, rye, and rice). In tuber and root crops, yield reduction in response to shading is less than proportional within an irradiance reduction greater than 10%. With irradiation values lower than 50% compared to full light, all the crops analysed in the study behave as susceptible (Laub et al., 2022).

Preliminary research have highlighted that crop growth and yield can benefit from APV conditions, in particular when drought, high temperature and high level of incoming radiation occur (Pataczek et al., 2023; Schweiger and Pataczek, 2023). Therefore, the positive impacts of APV seem to be pronounced in crops grown in arid environments (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2019; Barron-Gafford et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a) and in forage crops (Al Mamun et al., 2023; Edouard et al., 2023). Forage crops are usually not irrigated and produce multiple harvests per year, making the summer harvest under APVs especially advantageous in comparison. Leafy vegetables have also been found to be more profitable in APV cultivation due to increased leaf production and individual leaf size (Marrou et al., 2013b). This is due to crop adaptation strategies to shade condition that allows some shade-adapted crops to expand their leaf surface and leaf area index (Potenza et al., 2022; Prà et al., 2023; Semeraro et al., 2024).

The study by Laub et al. (2022) only considered two studies actually conducted in APV condition, while all the other studies involved experiments with shading nets, low artificial lighting and associated with agroforestry systems. A more recent analysis conducted by Dupraz (2023) focused exclusively on studies that involved APVs. Similarly to what was done by Laub et al., data from different APV studies were used to form a shading response function that relates crop productivity to the Ground Cover Ratio (GCR) of the system, assumed as a proxy for the level of shading to which the crops are subjected.

The GCR is a soil cover index calculated as the ratio between the surface area of the total number of photovoltaic modules to total land area occupied by the APV. The GCR is related with the percentage of shading (expressed as irradiation reduction) to the crops. However, in general, the average percentage of shading compared to full light conditions is higher than the percentage of GCR (Dupraz, 2023).

In this study, crops were not divided into categories, and the same weight was given to all the productive results of the analysed studies. Both studies are based on a limited number of data, and therefore, the results cannot be considered conclusive. However, it seems possible to determine, for each species, an average value of suitable shading that can be expressed as Plant GCR (Dupraz, 2023).

2.1. CROP MODELS FOR AGRIVOLTAICS

At present, agronomic studies on APV systems have been conducted throughout field trials (Edouard et al., 2023; Ferrara et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2022; Marrou et al., 2013b; Reeza et al., 2024; Willockx et al., 2023), simulations with computer platforms that integrate radiation models and crop models (Al Mamun et al., 2023; Amaducci et al., 2018; Campana et al., 2021; Dupraz et al., 2011; Ko et al., 2021; Potenza et al., 2022), and through techno-economic analyses (Ahmed et al., 2022; Poonia et al., 2022; Schindele et al., 2020). The core of these simulations lies in the integration of radiation models and crop models. Radiation models estimate the amount of sunlight available for plant growth under the shading conditions generated by the APVs panels. Crop models, on the other hand, are mathematical representations that simulate how crops develop and respond to the environment. These models typically predict potential crop yields under ideal conditions, as well as yields under various limitations, such as shading from the APVs panels (Asseng et al., 2014).

However, the availability of APV systems is scarce and limited to small experimental fields, so the empirical data collected in the field are few and limited on few crops.

The recent incentive of international policies for the development of APV has led to a significant increase in the number of scientific studies both in terms of the effects on agricultural production and the profitability of the systems (Ahmed et al., 2022; Edouard et al., 2023; Schindele et al., 2020).

In silico models of utility-scale agrivoltaic (APV) systems are emerging as crucial decision-support tools. These models facilitate the identification of the most profitable system configurations without requiring physical installation. By providing valuable insights into crop performance and energy production, simulations enable the optimization of APV design and management strategies for specific environmental conditions (Katsikogiannis et al., 2022). Scenario analysis driven by these simulations can identify the necessary APV system characteristics to achieve desired performance in terms of both energy conversion and agricultural yield.

To summarize, modelling approach for APV enables the prediction of:

- **Crop yield:** Several studies have successfully simulated crop yield under APV conditions, considering factors like shading patterns (Dinesh and Pearce, 2016; Dupraz et al., 2011).
- **Water availability and conservation:** Models can also be used to assess the impact of APVs on water use and potential water savings (Elamri et al., 2018; El-Gafy, 2017).
- **Light interception:** Simulations can estimate how much sunlight crops capture (irradiance interception) within an APV environment (Santra et al., 2021; Trommsdorff et al., 2021).
- **Economic viability:** The models can even be used to predict potential financial returns, considering both crop production revenue and the revenue generated from solar energy production (Cuppari et al., 2021; Dinesh and Pearce, 2016).

Existing research highlighted the effectiveness of crop models adapted in simulating how crops adjust their growth stages (phenological development) and yield in response to the shading patterns generated

by APVs. The Genotype-by-Environment interaction on CROp growth Simulator (GECROS), developed by Xinyou Yin and H.H. van Laar (2005), has been adopted for simulating maize and soy bean cultivated under APV (Amaducci et al., 2018; Potenza et al., 2022). The Environmental Policy Integrated Climate (EPIC) (<https://epicapex.tamu.edu/epic/>), was adopted for simulating oats and potato coupled with vertical APV system (Campana et al., 2021). The Agricultural Production Systems sIMulator (APSIM) (<https://www.apsim.info/>) was used for simulating sub-tropical grass on four different grazing strategies (Al Mamun et al., 2023). The Simulateur mulTidisciplinaire pour les Cultures Standard (STICS) (<https://stics.inrae.fr/>) (Brisson et al., 2003) was used to simulate wheat and lettuce under different APV conditions (Dinesh and Pearce, 2016; Dupraz et al., 2011), and the Decision Support System for Agrotechnology Transfer (DSSAT) (<https://dssat.net/>) was adopted for simulating paddy rice, barley, and soybean grown in AVP (Ko et al., 2021).

2.2. AGRIVOLTAIC PLANT

Experimental trials under APV conditions will be conducted at both UCSC and REM. In both cases, plants are characterised by overhead bi-axial technology.

2.2.1. @UCSC

At Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (**UCSC**) (45°02'16.1 "N 9°43'49.1 "E), a biaxial bifacial plant will be operational from summer 2024, the result of technology developed by REM Tec. The plant covers an area of 0.72 hectares, with a total production capacity of 506.97 kWp (Figure 2). The installed system comprises a total of 774 modules, each with a power output of 660 Wp (Trina model) and dimensions of 1.38 m by 2.3 m, providing a GCR of 33.4 %. Meteorological stations and agronomic sensors will be installed to monitor micrometeorological conditions and crop health under shaded conditions, to collect data on climatic and agronomic parameters.

The installation was realised with the Agrovoltaiico® 3D - T2.1 tracker version, characterised by a 10.5 metre horizontal tube supporting 4 rows of wings, totalling 24 panels per tracker. Within the plant, there are two sectors with different distances between tracker rows, 15 and 18 metres respectively. Considering the benefits of bifaciality, the installation at UCSC will be able to generate between 1694 and 1740 kWh/kWp. The 43 installed trackers are connected by a tensile structure, which supports the cabling while minimising the footprint. The height of the system, 5 metres above the ground, enables conventional agricultural machinery to operate below. The permitted rotation is +/- 50° from the horizontal and +/- 60° from the vertical axis.

Figure 2 . Top view of the agrivoltaic plant at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC)

2.2.2. @REM

At **REM tec (REM)**, the site in Virgilio (45° 5'40.12"N, 10°47'30.69"E) was established at the end of April 2011. The plant extends over 11,42 hectares, to produce 2,15 MWp (280 Wp polycrystalline modules) with a yearly producible of 1545 kWh/kWp. Since 2019, REM Tec decided to lead some experimentations on various varieties (tomato, pumpkin, potato, wheat, corn, rice, alfalfa, kiwis, apple, vineyard etc.). In this field of activity, a weather station and agronomic sensors were installed to measure climatic and agronomic parameters. The aim of these experiments is to understand how plants evolve under shade. From this data, the goal is to modify the tracking system depending on the crops to provide the right amount of shading and light.

This installation was built with the first version of the monofacial Agrovoltaico® 3D-T1.0 tracker (Figure 3), which consists of a 12-meter-long horizontal tube, which supports 5 rows of wings, each supporting a photovoltaic module, generally made up of 72 cells. The rows of trackers are 12 meters apart from each other. They are connected by a tensile structure to support the cabling and minimize the footprint. The height of the system is approximately 4-4.5m from the ground, allowing traditional agricultural machinery to work below. The rotation that can be allowed is of +/- 50 ° from the horizontal, and +/- 60° from the vertical axis. Over the years of operation, several crops were grown under the plants, such as wheat, corn, alfalfa, soybeans, and rice. Since 2019, REM Tec has also been carrying out experimental research on the Virgilio plant with horticultural crops, such as salad, potatoes, tomatoes, pumpkin, melons, raspberries as well as kiwi and grapes amongst others. The results remain preliminary and until confirmed by several harvests, research continues.

The installed system contains a total of 768 trackers, or 7680 modules (280 Wp modules). Compared to the surface area used by the technology, this provides a GCR of 14%. In this specific case, less than one

hectare is used and available for the experiments. Today, the system has evolved, to have first 4 secondary axes (technology 2.1, Figure 3) and now 3 secondary axes with bigger modules (660 Wp and soon 700 Wp) with a size of 1.38m by 2.3 meters that provide a GCR of 30% approximately.

Figure 3. Technology 1.0 installed in Virgilio (Mantova, Italy)

2.3. OBJECTIVES OF THE EXPERIMENTAL TRIALS: GENERAL ASPECTS

The experimental trials that will be conducted within the Italian demonstration sites have the main objectives to study the yield and growth response of horticultural cash crops (potato, tomato and aromatic plants) food and industrial crops (soybean and hemp) under the shaded condition of the APV plants present at UCSC and REM.

Moreover, crops potentially suitable for biomethane production (maize, sorghum and wheat) will be cultivated within APV for assessing their suitability and performance.

Data collected during the experiments will be used to calibrate and validate crop models, to define agronomic protocols for the cultivation under APV and to evaluate the best integration strategies between APV and biomethane production. Two integration strategies between agrivoltaics and biomethane production will be analysed: i) cultivation of cash crops under small-scale agrivoltaic plants coupled to biomethane plants; ii) implementation of crop rotations (or variants best suited to agrivoltaic conditions) proposed by the CIB for biomethane production, to cultivate medium and large-scale agrivoltaic plants (20 hectares and up) in order to produce not only electricity for the biomethane plant, but also for the grid.

3. MONITORING OF AGRIVOLTAIC CONDITIONS

3.1. CROP MEASUREMENTS IN AGRIVOLTAIC CONDITIONS

In the comprehensive monitoring of the agrivoltaics system, an extensive array of parameters (Table 1) will be systematically collected via sensors, sampling and observation to facilitate a thorough comparison and analysis of its performance. The input variables within the cropping component encompass essential factors such as manure input, fertilizer input, and mechanical cultivation practices. These inputs are integral components of the agronomic management strategies employed within the system, contributing to the overall health and productivity of the associated crops. On the output side, the cropping component is assessed through various variables including crop yield, crop productivity, crop efficiency, and crop quality. These parameters offer a holistic understanding of the overall performance of the crops grown within the agrivoltaics system. Additionally, the electricity generation component is evaluated using variables such as DC side string current and voltage and AC side string current and voltage. This provides insights into the efficiency and electrical performance of the photovoltaic panels integrated into the system. In tandem with the cropping and energy components, inherent pedo-climatic parameters and variables play a crucial role in characterising the environmental conditions. Soil-related factors, including physical attributes like soil type and moisture levels provide insights into the soil health and nutrient/water dynamics. Meteorological variables, ranging from irradiance and temperature to wind speed and precipitation, offer a comprehensive overview of the microclimatic conditions influencing the agrivoltaics system. This intricate dataset ensures a robust foundation for investigating, comparing, and analysing the multifaceted performances of agrivoltaic system. Table 1 shows the main crop (C), agronomic (A), photovoltaic (P) and micrometeorological (M) parameters that will be monitored during the growing season.

Table 1. Main parameters collected under agrivoltaic condition. Crop (C), Agronomic (A), Photovoltaic (P), Soil (S) and Micrometeorological (M) parameters.

Variable	Variable type	Description
Crop yield and crop biomass	C	Crop yield will be assessed at harvest by evaluating wet and/or dry yield, depending on the crop. Crop biomass will also be assessed during the growing season at specific phenological stages of interest. If necessary, samples will be separated into storage organs (e.g. grain, tubers) and aerial biomass (using standard procedures) and both parts of the plant will be dried in an oven at 65° Celsius to constant weight.

Crop quality	C	Depending on the crop, quality assessment will be evaluated on harvested products. For example, the size of the tuber for potatoes, while for maize or wheat the starch or protein content.
Crop phenology	C	Record dates of key events such as emergence, flowering, fruiting, and maturity.
Crop morphology and physiology	C	Specific leaf area (SLA), Leaf Area Index (LAI), leaf width and leaf length
Leaf temperature	C	Leaf temperature will be measured using thermal imaging.
Mechanical cultivation	A	The type of intervention, tool, process and timing will be recorded.
Fertiliser input	A	The type, the amount and the timing of fertilisers will be recorded.
Manure input	A	The type, characteristics, amount and timing of manure applied will be recorded.
Pesticide use	A	The type, amount and timing of potential pesticide applications will be recorded.
Nutritional status	C	Proximal and remote sensing sensor will be used. Soil Plant Analysis Development (SPAD) and Red Green Blue (RGB) and/or multispectral camera will be used to estimate the nutritional status. Drone-based thermal and multispectral images throughout key times during growing season.
Soil texture	S	Using a standard methodology to assess the grain size and texture by sieving, sedimentation and particle centrifugation.
Soil moisture	S	Soil moisture probes
Soil nutrients	S	Laboratory analysis
Soil pH	S	Potentiometric determination of pH in H ₂ O
Irradiance	M	Global horizontal irradiance (GHI) is measured via a pyranometer sensor, which is used to measure the irradiance (W/m ²)
Diffuse radiation	M	Diffused horizontal irradiance (DHI) is measured using another pyranometer, a shadow ring/band is used to prevent direct radiation from reaching it. Therefore, the shaded pyranometer will only measure diffuse radiation.
Reflected solar radiation (albedo)	M	Albedometer will be used to measure reflected solar radiation (W/m ²).
Photosynthetic active radiation (PAR)	M	Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) sensors will be used to measure within a range of 400-700 nm. The PAR sensor will share information about the irradiances, which will help the crop perform photosynthesis.

Temperature	M	Air temperature will be measured using thermocouple sensors.
Wind speed	M	Wind speed and wind direction will be measured using anemometers.
Wind direction	M	Measurement of wind speed in m/s and wind direction in degrees. Wind speed and direction will be measured outside the agri-voltaic plant.
Air humidity	M	Air humidity and dew point will be measured using thermohygrometers. Hygrometers will be used to measure the humidity or amount of water vapor in the air.
Dew point	M	
Precipitation	M	Tipping bucket (measuring rainfall).

This approach will help elucidate how APV systems influence the microclimate and, consequently, crop development. Monitoring the growth and development of crops under APV is a useful practice for evaluating the ongoing impact on crop phenology and yield. There are several key indicators to be measured throughout the growth cycle of each studied crop. These indicators include phenological stage, morphological adaptations to shading (crop height, Leaf Area Index [LAI], Specific Leaf Area [SLA]), crop yield and biochemical adaptations (chlorophyll content).

The following paragraphs provide a detailed discussion of these main parameters. Subsequently, each crop's specific experimental protocol will be deepened in the following chapters.

3.1.1. Crop phenology

During previous studies on APV it was noted that shaded crops under PV modules may experience maturity delay due to shading (Marrou et al., 2013a; Weselek et al., 2021a). A general delay was found in APV maize crop for different phenological stage compared to full sun condition. Compared to full sun treatment, shaded maize delayed the achievement of emergence (VE), tasselling (VT) and silking (R1) stages (Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023).

The data of each phenological development stage evolution will be recorded among APV plots. Timing for harvesting crop is related to phenological stage and a delayed maturity could entail separate harvesting for full light plot and APV plot. Furthermore, even considering a single APV plot, variations in shading levels occurring among sub-plots, can lead to differences in phenological stage in the same plot. To ensure consistent data collection, phenological stages are being recorded according to a standardized scale like the Biologische Bundesanstalt, Bundessortenamt and Chemical industry (BBCH) scale. In the BBCH the full developmental cycle of the crop is subdivided into ten clearly recognizable and distinguishable developmental phases (Meier et al., 2009):

- 0: Germination / sprouting / bud development;
- 1: Leaf development (main shoot);
- 2: Formation of side shoots / tillering;
- 3: Stem elongation or rosette growth / shoot development (main shoot);

- 4: Development of harvestable vegetative plant parts or vegetatively propagated organs / booting (main shoot);
- 5: Inflorescence emergence (main shoot) / heading;
- 6: Flowering (main shoot);
- 7: Development of fruit;
- 8: Ripening or maturity of fruit and seed;
- 9: Senescence, beginning of dormancy.

BBCH scale is commonly used as a combination of principal growth stages (from 0-9) further subdivided in secondary stages (from 0-9) to create two-digit codes that describe specific points in a plant's development. Even secondary stages can be further subdivided (e.g., for crops like potatoes) to form a three-digit code to indicate the phenological stage (Meier et al., 2009). As example, a comprehensive BBCH scale of three digits was developed for soybean by Munger et al. (1997).

A specific phenological stage is considered achieved when at least 50% of the plants within a plot exhibit the characteristic traits associated with that stage, according to the reference BBCH scale. For each investigated crop, each APV subplot and full-light plot are screened to monitor the developmental stage. Plants are counted, and if 50% or more of the plants within a subplot display the characteristics of a particular phenological stage, that stage is considered reached for the entire subplot.

3.1.2. Crop height

Crop height is a morphological and shade-adaptive trait which is most affected under a shaded environment (Franklin, 2008; Gommers et al., 2013; Weselek et al., 2021a) and under an APV system (Weselek et al., 2021a, 2021b) since crops tend to elongate their stems by cell distension when light decreases. To study the effect of the APV system on crop height, measurements will be taken during the growing cycle on a specific number of occasions according to the growth curve of the crop.

Height at harvest under APV condition is expected to be higher than the full sun control. On the one hand, previous experience involving field trials of wheat and potato crops stated a higher height for those plants under APV shading condition (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a). On the other hand, another study showed different results for maize. A field experiment conducted on maize showed less tall plants on average for APV plots compared to full sun control (Grubbs et al., 2024) and similar results were reported from (Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023).

3.1.3. Leaf Area Index (LAI)

Leaf Area Index (LAI) is a metric used to indicate the total surface area of plant leaves per unit of ground surface area, is an indicator of canopy density, typically expressed in square meters per square meter ($m^2 m^{-2}$). This variable can be measured using either destructive or non-destructive methods.

- **Destructive methods:** Can be achieved using specialized leaf scanners (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024) or through digital image processing techniques. Plants have to be collected entirely to process the leaves with these techniques.

- **Non-destructive methods:** These methods offer the advantage of allowing LAI measurements at various stages of plant growth (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Reher et al., 2024). Examples of non-destructive tools include canopy analysers like the LAI-2200C (Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023; Weselek et al., 2021a), ceptometers like the Sun Scan Dela-T Devices (Potenza et al., 2022), and hemispherical photography. Using non-destructive methods, allows the generation of a LAI increment curves over time (Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023; Weselek et al., 2021a) without harvesting the plants.

In shaded condition, LAI has been found to be higher for some species in comparison with full sun control, as reported by (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Li et al., 2010; Potenza et al., 2022; Weselek et al., 2021a). Specifically, for wheat and potato LAI is expected to be higher in average for shaded plots in comparison with full sun control, as reported by (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Li et al., 2010; Weselek et al., 2021a). This behaviour has been explained as a morpho-physiological response that plant exert on shaded environment in order to capture more light and compensate for reduced light incidence. It appears to be both specific and varietal factor as reported for wheat by (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024) where this adaptation appeared more pronounced in "elder varieties" compared to modern hybrids.

LAI should be recorded at key growth stages: before and during flowering, and during fruit or grain development. Regular LAI measurements help assess the canopy's response to the shading condition experienced in APV. It can be measured using portable devices such as a Ceptometer (Accupar LP-80). This device allows for LAI field measurements by capturing light transmission through the canopy to estimate leaf coverage.

3.1.4. Specific Leaf Area

Specific leaf area (SLA), also known as Leaf Mass Area (LMA), represents the leaf area per unit of dry mass; it is indicative of leaf thickness. It is measured through destructive analysis by sampling fresh leaves. Fresh leaves are first scanned through a leaf scanner or through image processing software such as ImageJ software (National Institute of Health, USA), and then dried to obtain the leaf dry mass.

In most species, SLA is negatively related to light availability. When light is limiting, having a large leaf area per mass of leaves improves light interception for plants (Poorter et al., 2009). Wheat for example, showed this adaptation to shading under controlled environment (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2019).

A study on an apple APV orchard, located in Mediterranean France, showed that fluctuating shading resulted in reduced photosynthetic capacity of leaves and increased their specific leaf area (thinner leaves) (Juillion et al., 2022).

(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021) reported SLA (LMA) modification for shaded wheat respect to control treatment due to increased leaves area. Leaves changed in response to light conditions and were found to be thinner than full light control for wheat in mediterranean environment. This adaptation can be explained as shaded plants have to develop bigger leaves to compensate and intercept more PAR.

3.1.5. SPAD Chlorophyll Content

The chlorophyll content in leaves, which determines their photosynthetic capacity (Li et al., 2018), is linked to the N nutrition status of the plant and is affected by shading. According to studies carried out in moderately shaded environments with peony (Wan et al., 2020) under low light conditions for a large number of species (Niinemets and Valladares, 2004) and in an intercropping system (maize, soybean) (Fan et al., 2019), the chlorophyll content tends to increase as the light availability decreases.

Chlorophyll content can be measured indirectly using a Soil Plant Analysis Development (SPAD-502) portable chlorophyll meter, which provides SPAD units related to chlorophyll content. Alternatively, the Chlorophyll Concentration Meter from Apogee Instruments, Logan, UT can also be used to perform similar analyses and assess the Chlorophyll concentration index (CCI) (Grubbs et al., 2024).

The way measurements are taken is significant and each species may have different requirements for field chlorophyll analysis. Measure should be taken from fully expanded leaves (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Uddling et al., 2007), leaves veins must be avoided for accurate measurements (Uddling et al., 2007). SPAD has been indicated as a reliable way to assess chlorophyll content for wheat and potato crop (Uddling et al., 2007). Leaf chlorophyll content is expected to be higher in shaded wheat plots than in full sun plots (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024). Moreover, the chlorophyll content of the flag leaf can be a crucial indicator of adaptation to shade. In fact in shaded condition the chlorophyll content of the flag leaf is expected to be higher than the control (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Li et al., 2010). In a study involving maize crop cultivated with APV, the Chlorophyll concentration index (CCI), measured with MC-100 device, showed no difference between treatments (Grubbs et al., 2024).

3.1.6. Yield and yield components

Reduction in overall yield for both APV (Reher et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a) and agroforestry condition (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Dufour et al., 2013) are reported in literature for different crops. However, the extent of yield reduction is strongly influenced by species, cultivar and climate condition. In a study by Li et al. (2010) different behaviour is reported for shade tolerant wheat cultivar compared to shade intolerant cultivars. When shading is not severe the grain yield can be improved for both genetically adaptation (Li et al., 2010) or climatic condition. In fact during an adverse growth cycle due to extreme temperatures and drought stress, wheat produced more in APV shaded plots than full light control plots in (Weselek et al., 2021a). There are also studies that reported no differences on wheat yield for plots under APV compared to full sun control ones (Pataczek et al., 2023). Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2021) reported higher vegetative biomass and grain biomass for shaded wheat compared to full sun control. Shaded wheat (25% and 50% shaded) yielded more than control full light treatment. It is worth to mention that the study was conducted in hot climate environment.

Studies conducted outside the Mediterranean area reported that slight pre-flowering shading (20%) (Mu et al., 2010) or increased (Li et al., 2010) do not affected wheat biomass yield compared to full light conditions, while more intense shading led to biomass decreases.

Despite being indicated as shade intolerant crop previous experience on maize in APV reported promising results. APV when with a low GCR could increase biomass and yield of maize (+5.7 %) compared with

the control grown in full sun. Conversely a denser solar panels configuration had a negative effect on biomass and yield. The increased yield observed under low-density solar panels is likely due to a combination of factors, including improved light use efficiency (LUE) by maize plants and reduced soil water evaporation due to shading (Sekiyama and Nagashima, 2019). Similar findings were reported by (Kim et al., 2021), who observed a yield increase in maize grown under APVs with a shading level of 21.3%. However, their study also found that yields declined at higher shading levels. (Jo et al., 2022) conducted a two-year study and did not observe significant differences in maize plant size or yield when grown under APVs compared to full sun. In APV systems, the shading treatment, which can vary depending on the partial shading caused by solar panels in different sections, affects plant photosynthesis. Planting density also interacts with this factor: higher densities can intensify competition for light, potentially reducing yield per plant but increasing it per area if management is optimal. The use of high-density hybrids can be employed to better withstand the shading levels of the installation.

Dry matter of leaves, culms and grains:

In literatures a lower Harvest Index (HI) for crop grown under APV has been reported for wheat in comparison to full sun control (Artru et al., 2017; Weselek et al., 2021a). In the study of (Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024) a higher dry weight has been found for some wheat variety in shaded agroforestry system compared to full sun control. Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2021) found that harvest index was higher for shaded wheat compared to full sun control treatment.

In maize, Total Dry Matter (TDM) and Dry Grain Yield (GY) were reduced when less radiation was available for plants, thus in comparison with the full sun control, a moderate shading rates still decrease drastically the total dry matter per plant (Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023).

Weight of 1000 grains, proxy for grain size: Yield decline could be related to both number of grains per ear and grain weight. Thousand grain weight was significantly lower under shading in various study of both APV or agroforestry for maize and wheat (Artru et al., 2017; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a). Most likely the decreased single grain weights is the main cause of reduction in grain yields of winter wheat under shading (Dufour et al., 2013; Li et al., 2010; Weselek et al., 2021a). There are cases where thousand grain weight increase with shading. For instance, in the study of Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2021), the grain weight was higher than full light control for the plot at 25% shading.

Environmental Monitoring: can be carried out by setting up at least three weather stations. One installed at full light (FL) plot and two beneath the APV at different test areas. Suitable weather station to be installed are the Delta-T weather and the Watch-Dog weather station (**Figure 4**). Environmental monitoring involves relative humidity, solar irradiance, wind speed, air temperature and rainwater. Moreover, additional sensor should be placed in the soil for available water monitoring along the soil profile.

Figure 4. Watch-Dog weather station (left), Delta-T weather station (right).

3.2. DEFINING THE OPTIMAL NUMBER OF AREA FOR MONITORING AGRIVOLTAIC CONDITIONS

In the growing environment under APV conditions, the panels create shading reduction zones that depend on the configuration and spatialisation of the panels. To assess the effect of shading, the experimental areas will be divided into bands parallel to the main cultivation axis. For experimental purposes, these bands will be considered as treatments (Figure 5). For agronomic management, these are represented by N rows (e.g. potato, maize or tomato) or a fixed distance in wheat. Using the simulation platform described in Amaducci et al. (2018), global and diffuse radiation will be simulated under APV conditions with a time step of 30 min and a spatial resolution of 0.15 m - 0.2 m. The radiation values will then be used to calculate the shadow depth values needed to characterise the cultivation strips.

Figure 5. Shade-depth map obtained in the study by Potenza et al. (2022). The experimental area was divided into four cultivation zones. For each of them, a shade-dept value was estimated with the simulation platform described in Amaducci et al. (2018).

Given the heterogeneity of radiation within the APV system, it is essential to identify the optimal number of points where to place sensors to monitor the parameters of interest (global and diffuse radiation, air and soil temperature). To ensure effective monitoring of microclimatic conditions, the sensors will be strategically placed, based on the shading and radiation variability maps generated by the UCSC simulation platform (Figure 6), to monitor APV conditions in the most representative manner.

Figure 6. Map of the global radiation (W m^{-2}) variability of the agri-voltaic plant at UCSC generated by the UCSC simulation platform

The monthly radiation maps (Figure 7) were used as information layers within specific algorithms for smart sampling. The smart sampling method employed is the Conditional Latin Hypercube Sampling (CLHS). CLHS is a technique commonly used in statistics and computer simulations to efficiently sample from a multidimensional parameter space. It is an extension of the Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) method, which aims to ensure a more uniform coverage of the parameter space than simple random sampling. In CLHS, the sampling process is guided or conditioned by additional information or parameter constraints (e.g. the global and diffuse radiation pattern produced by the simulation platform). By incorporating this additional information, the CLHS can improve sampling efficiency and ensure that samples are extracted in regions of interest or importance within the parameter space. The main steps of the CLHS method include:

- Defining the parameter space: Identify the interval and size of the parameter space to be sampled.
- Division into intervals: Divide each parameter dimension into intervals of equal probability.
- Generation of Latin hypercube: Create a Latin hypercube in the parameter space, ensuring that each interval in each dimension is represented by exactly one sample.
- Conditioning: Apply additional constraints or conditions to guide the sampling process. This might involve incorporating prior knowledge, specifying regions of interest or ensuring compatibility with known data.
- Sampling: Generate samples within the hypercube by satisfying specified conditions. This may involve iterative adjustments of the sampling distribution to meet the conditioning criteria.

- Analysis: Evaluate the sampled points to assess their distribution and coverage of parameter space. If necessary, adjust parameters or sampling conditions.

Figure 7. Monthly average 'Shade depth', 15 m pitch area. Resolution 0.2 m at UCSC

Using the CLHS method iteratively, the location and number of sampling points was verified to influence the ability to describe the entire multidimensional matrix. The sampling points selected with the CLHS method were compared to the entire simulated data matrix via the data platform. By comparing the values of the radiation parameters at the sampling points with the data distribution of the entire matrix, metrics were calculated to assess the representativeness of the sampling as the sample size increased:

- Relative standard error (%): $(\text{std_error} / \text{mean}) * 100$
- absolute mean percentage difference (%): $((\text{mean sampling} - \text{mean whole area}) / \text{mean whole area}) * 100$.

Figure 8 displays how as the number of global and diffuse radiation sampling points increases, the sampling error and thus the representativeness of the sampling itself decreases, reaching a plateau at 5 for the absolute mean percentage difference and 7 for the relative standard error.

Figure 8. Absolute mean percentage difference (%) and relative standard error (%) with increasing number of sampling points

3.3. CROP-SPECIFIC PROTOCOLS

3.3.1. Winter wheat

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is the most widely cultivated arable crop globally and is frequently included in crop rotation programs of several Countries. Wheat in Europe was cultivated in 2022 on a massive area of 62.749.238 ha (FAOSTAT, 2022). Due to its central role in global food security, wheat has been extensively studied under various growing conditions. These studies include investigations into wheat yield performance in shaded environments, such as agroforestry systems, shade net applications, and most recently, APV. Several studies have investigated the effects of shading on winter wheat yield. Here's a summary of the key findings:

Negative Impacts of Shading:

- **Reduced Yield:** Most studies reported significant yield reductions under shading, ranging from 25% to 45% with moderate shading (43-61%) and even higher with more intense shading (Artru et al., 2017; Beed et al., 2007; Lázaro et al., 2010; Li et al., 2010; Mu et al., 2010).
- **Cultivar Variability:** Wheat shade adapted variety can be identified. These cultivars generally experience lower yield losses compared to shade-intolerant varieties under similar shading conditions (Li et al., 2010; Mu et al., 2010).
- **Delayed Maturity:** Shading can delay wheat maturity, potentially impacting harvest timing (Marrou et al., 2013a; Weselek et al., 2021a).

Positive Impacts of Shading:

- **Increased Yield in Specific Conditions:** In some cases, studies conducted in agroforestry have observed yield increases of up to 19% under moderate shading in a Mediterranean climate (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2019; Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021). This suggests potential benefits for wheat under specific environmental conditions.

Mixed Results with APV:

- Pioneering studies using durum wheat in APV reported yield reductions of 8-19% (Dupraz et al., 2011; Marrou et al., 2013a).
- Yield reduction of 18-19% for wheat has been reported in a double year field trial in Germany; however, considering the energy generation, the overall Land equivalent Ratio (LER) was found increased compared to separated land use (Trommsdorff et al., 2021).
- Multi-year field trials in Germany with winter wheat did not show significant yield differences with control plots grown in full sun (Pataczek et al., 2023).

- Increased biomass has been observed for winter wheat grown in APV (Weselek et al., 2021a).
- Yield and Grain Size: However, these studies also often report decreased yields or smaller grain size, suggesting potential trade-offs between biomass and harvestable product.

The impact of shading on wheat yield appears complex and depends on several factors. These include shading intensity, cultivar selection, and environmental conditions. While some studies show promising results for particular shade adapted cultivars or specific climates, more research is needed to optimize wheat production within APV systems.

3.3.1.1 Experimental Design and data collection.

The Experimental field will be established in 2024 in a commercial APV field of 20 ha located in Monticelli d’Ongina, near Piacenza, Italy, where previous studies were conducted (Potenza et al., 2022). The experimental design is a split-plot design replicated four times having shading depth (Global irradiance reduction [%]) as treatment. Within each plot, four sub-plots, with different shading depth, will be marked. The four sub plots are identified according to the study of (Potenza et al., 2022) as depicted in Figure 5. Crop measurements and monitoring during growth cycle are listed in Table 2. Post harvest measurements are listed in Table 3.

Table 2. Pre harvest Measurements for wheat crop under APV. Each sub-plot stands for a different light treatment, or shading depth.

Variable	Time of measure	Method	Reference
Developmental stage	Every 4 week from tillering (stage 2). Every 2 weeks after Stem elongation (stage3).	According to BBCH scale, as described in section 3.1.1.	(Marrou et al., 2013a; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Leaf Area Index (LAI)	Every 4 weeks from the end of tillering. Every two week from flowering onwards.	By using a ceptometer device, or similar such as the LAI-2200C Plant Canopy Analyzer, for each sub-plot.	(Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Reher et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Chlorophyll content	Measured three times at specific phenological stages: heading, flowering, and grain filling.	By using a SPAD-502 or MC-100 portable devices. From the flag leaf of three main culm for each sub-plot. Measurement is performed two times for each flag leaf when fully expanded: one at one-third of the leaf length and at two-thirds of the leaf length. The two measures are then averaged. Leaves veins must be avoided.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Uddling et al., 2007)

Specific Leaf Area (SLA), also known as Leaf Mass Area (LMA)	Measured once at anthesis stage.	Measured from the flag leaf of three main culm for each sub-plot. Fresh leaves are first scanned through ImageJ software or leaf scanner, to measure each fresh leaf area. The leaves are then oven dried to constant weight to obtain leaf dry mass. The ratio of leaf dry mass to leaf area is the Specific Leaf Area (SLA).	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Poorter et al., 2009)
--	----------------------------------	--	---

Table 3. Post harvest measurements. From randomly selected plant samples for each sub-plot, the following measurements are taken once, after harvest or just before.

Variable	Method	Reference
Main culm height	Measured on the main culm of three randomly selected plants per sub-plot. Measure is taken from the coleoptile to the spike top, excluding awns.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Prakash et al., 2023; Reher et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Main Spike length	Spike length is measured for three randomly selected main culms per each sub-plot and control plots. Awns must be excluded.	(Reher et al., 2024)
Number of grains per spike	Measured from three main culm spike for each sub-plot and control plots.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Reher et al., 2024)
Total grain yield	Yield is measured by harvesting and weighing each sub-plot and control plots. The yield per hectare is then estimated.	(Dal Prà et al., 2024; Pataczek et al., 2023; Reher et al., 2024)
Dry matter of leaves, culms and grains	Each component measured from three randomly selected plants per sub-plot and control plot. Culms, their corresponding leaves, and grains are separated and oven-dried at 105°C until constant weight. Dry matter is then evaluated as percentage for each component.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024)
Harvest Index (HI)	Is calculated as the ratio of dry matter in the harvested grains to the total dry matter of the entire above-ground plant.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024)
Weight of 1000 grains, proxy for grain size	For each sub-plot and control plot, a thousand grains sample is randomly collected and weighed Preferably by using tools such as the <u>GAC 500XT</u> or similar.	(Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021; Dos Santos Neto et al., 2024; Reher et al., 2024; Weselek et al., 2021a)

3.3.2. Maize

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a globally significant crop, playing essential roles in human nutrition, animal feed production, and as an industrial raw material. Maize is widely cultivated in Europe occupying a total area of 17.533.920 ha (FAOSTAT, 2022). Its productivity is heavily influenced by numerous agronomic factors, including planting density and the amount of available solar irradiation.

Planting density has a significant impact on corn yield. Higher planting densities often lead to increased competition for resources like light, water, and nutrients, which can ultimately limit yield potential (Tokatlidis et al., 2011). Conversely, shading can alter photosynthesis, plant morphology, and ultimately, crop yield (Gao et al., 2017; Yuan et al., 2012).

Previous studies have shown how variations in planting density can affect the growth and development of corn, altering the plant architecture and responses to environmental stress (Cox, 1996; Echarte et al., 2000). Moreover, the impact of shading, both natural and artificial, on the photosynthetic performance and qualitative characteristics of corn has been examined (Gao et al., 2017). These studies suggest that the interaction between planting density and light levels can have complex effects on corn physiology and productivity for maize.

The aim of this experiment is to study how the shade generated by the installation affects the morphology, physiology, and yield of two corn hybrids, FAO 500, at different planting densities cultivated with an APV system on a large scale.

Description of the Experiment

The study will be conducted at RemTec's commercial APV field in Monticelli D'Ongina, Italy (45°04'10" N -9°55'40" E). The field features a bifacial solar tracking system, which will be used to assess the performance of two distinct FAO 500 corn hybrids: Pioneer P0937 and Dekalb DKC6092 (high density). These two hybrids will be cultivated at three different planting densities namely 6, 8, and 12 plants per square meter. For each hybrid and plant density treatment a control plot (450 m² for each hybrid) will be set up far from the APV to avoid shading. Each full light (FL) control plot will be replicated four times with a surface of 144 m² each as shown in Figure 9. The APV is characterized by five different shading depths (AV5 = 29.5%, AV4 = 23.1%, AV3 = 16.1%, AV2 = 15.3%, AV1 = 22%), as reported in Figure 9 **Fout!** **Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** Crop measurements and monitoring during growth cycle are listed in Table 4. Post harvest measurements are listed in Table 5.

Figure 9. Maize experimental design depicting sowing densities (left) and shading depth treatments (right). Sowing densities: D12 = 12 plants m⁻², D8 = 8 plants m⁻², D6 = 6 plants m⁻². Shading depth treatments (from left to right): AV5 = 29.5%, AV4 = 23.1%, AV3 = 16.1%, AV2 = 15.3%, AV1 = 22.0%.

Table 4. Pre harvest Measurements for Maize crop under APV. Each sub-plot stands for a different light treatment, or shading depth.

Variable	Time of measure	Method	Reference
Leaf Area Index (LAI)	Measured at four developmental stages: at vegetative emergence (VE), at six leaf stage (V6), at Tasseling (VT) and at milk stage (R3).	By using a Ceptometer device (Accupar LP-80) preferably under clear sky conditions at noon. Measures are taken by placing the ceptometer sensor parallel to crop row orientation within the central line between two rows for each sub-plot and control plots.	(Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023)
Chlorophyll content	Every two week from VE to R3 stage.	By using a SPAD-502 (Konica Minolta) or MC-100 (Apogee instruments) portable devices. Measurement is taken from the second fully expanded leaf from the top of three plants per sub-plot and control plot. For each leaf, three measures at different sections are taken and averaged.	nd
Plant Height and Leaf Number	Plant height will be measured every two weeks from stage VE to physiological maturity. Leaf number monitoring will be carried from V2 (2-leaf	Plant height is measured at the top-collared leaf. Total number of leaves per plant are counted, including only those leaves with a visible collar.	(Grubbs et al., 2024; Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023), Smith et al., 2010)

	stage) until first visible flowers appearance.		
Specific Leaf Area (SLA), also known as leaf mass area (LMA).	Measurements will be taken at two stages: at V6 and physiological maturity.	The third leaf from the tassel is Collected for each from each sub-plot and control plot. Leaf area is measured using a leaf area meter. Subsequently leaves are oven dried until constant weight. The ratio of leaf area to its dry weight correspond to SLA.	(Perez-Harguindeguy, N. et al. 2013)

Table 5. Post harvest measurements. From randomly selected plant samples for each sub-plot, the following measurements are taken once.

Variable	Method	Reference
Grain Yield	Within each sub-plot and control plot, a 2 m ² area is manually harvested. Individual plants are sampled, and separated into leaves, stem, and ears. Each component is then weighed. At last, when grain yield is obtained for each sub-plot, the yield per hectare is assessed for comparability.	(Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023)
Total Dry Matter (TDM)	leaves, stems, and ears, harvested from each sub-plot, are separated and oven-dried until constant weight. Subsequently they are weighed individually to determine the dry weight of yield components. Dry kernels are separated from the cobs to estimate the dry matter of Grain the Harvest index (HI) is then calculated as the ratio of GY and aerial TDM at maturity.	(Ramos-Fuentes et al., 2023) (Kawano, 1990)
1000 Kernel Weight (TKW)	2 sub-samples from each sub-plot (light treatment and density) are collected and processed to shuck the cobs. Fresh weight of 1000 kernels from each sub-sample are recorded. The sub-samples are then oven dried until constant weigh end weighed.	(Maddonna et al., 1998)

3.3.3. Potato

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is an important industrial crop well distributed around Europe. In 2022, a surface of 4.063.302 ha (FAOSTAT, 2022), has been used for growing potato in Europe.

Studies conducted in APV fields have shown that potato yields may decrease due to shading, but APV can also sustain yields when limiting factors like heat and drought are involved.

Early research on shading effects on potato used artificial shade. While tuber number and yield generally decreased under shade (Kuruppuarachchi, 1990; Midmore, 1984), regions with high solar irradiation saw yield increases when shading was applied during early growth or around midday (Kuruppuarachchi, 1990; Midmore et al., 1988). This was attributed to enhanced plant survival due to shading. Additionally, Sale (1973) found that shading early in the growth cycle did not affect tuber initiation.

Schulz et al. (2019) conducted a three-year field experiment investigating the effects of various artificial shading levels on potato growth. They found significant changes only at 50% shade, resulting in delayed flowering and senescence, and a reduction in tuber number and mass. However, starch content remained unaffected, and parameters like stem number, plant height, and foliage mass were not influenced by shading up to 26%. This suggests that potatoes can tolerate moderate shading and be successfully integrated into APV systems.

Similar findings were reported by Lee et al., (2022) who observed that for potato crops grown under 31.6% shading in APV systems, most growth and yield parameters were similar to unshaded controls, except for a doubling of plant height under APV.

Contrasting results were found by Weselek et al. (2021a) in a two-year study in Germany. While potato yield decreased by 20% in 2017 under APV conditions compared to full-sun controls, it increased by 11% in the hot, dry summer of 2018, highlighting the influence of climate on APV crop performance. Additionally, morphological changes like increased plant height and leaf area index (LAI) were observed in shaded plants, consistent with earlier studies using shading nets (Kuruppuarachchi, 1990, Midmore et al. 1988). APV potato plots also showed delayed leaf senescence without affecting tuber maturity.

Trommsdorff et al. (2021) also investigated APV effects on potatoes, reporting a 25% yield decrease, although this included land losses due to APV structures. When considering yield per unit of cultivated land area, the reduction was closer to 15%, suggesting promise for potato cultivation under APV, particularly in dry and warm environments.

Experimental design

This study investigates the vegetative growth and production performances of potato crops under APV systems with varying degrees of GCR. The full light control will be set up with four replicated plots far from the APV to avoid shading. It will encompass a surface of (2.7 m x 8 m/10 m). An area of 12 x 14 m (pitch x tracker length), replicated four times, will be further subdivided in sub-plots accounting for the shading

depth within the distance from two consecutive PV array. Experimental design of potato trial is depicted in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden..**

Figure 10. Schematic representation of the experimental design for potato crop in APV.

Potato planting density will consist in 4.4-4.5 plants/m². 12 rows per plot, with 0.9 m distance between rows and 0.25 m-0.3 m distance within rows. Rows will be oriented parallel to the main axis of the APV. The study aims to estimate potato yield under different treatments, characterized by different shading intensities.

Main monitored parameters will be discussed in detail in the following section. Measurements for potato experimental trials in APV are listed in Table 6 and 7, for pre-harvest measurement and post-harvest measurement respectively.

Table 6. Pre harvest Measurements for potato crop under APV.

Variable	Time of measure	Method	Reference
BBCH monitoring	Every fourth week until flowering. Every second week from flowering onward.	According to BBCH scale, as described in section 3.1.1.	(Kacheyo et al., 2021; Schulz et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a)

Plant height	Every fourth week until flowering. Every second week from flowering onward.	Measured on the main stem of ten tagged plants for each sub-plot. From the soil to the highest point of the plant canopy	(Lee et al., 2022; Schulz et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Leaf Area Index (LAI)	Every fourth week until flowering. Every second week from flowering onward.	Measured at one central spot for each sub-plot (shading-depth treatment) and control plots by using a LAI-2200C Plant Canopy Analyzer, LI-COR	(Weselek et al., 2021a)
Chlorophyll content	Every fourth week until flowering. Every second week from flowering onward.	By using portable instrument: SPAD Chlorophyll meter, Konika Minolta.	(Lee et al., 2022)
Specific Leaf Area (SLA)	Once at harvest	The area of a leaf per plant is determined. Leaf is then dried in oven until constant weight and the dry mass is determined.	(Schulz et al., 2019)

Table 7. Post harvest measurements for potato.

Variable	Method	Reference
Total fresh weight tubers	A representative sample for each sub-plot is harvested at maturity. Weighing is done after cleaning soil residues.	(Lee et al., 2022; Schulz et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Discarded tubers and marketable fractions	Tubers having a diameter lower than 35 mm, disease affected or malformed are discarded	(Schulz et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a)
Number of tubers per sub-plot	Counted for 3 plants per sub-plot	(Schulz et al., 2019)
Identification of tuber diameter classes	Harvested potatoes are cleaned of soil residues and sorted by diameter: <35 mm, 35-50 mm, > 50 mm	(Schulz et al., 2019; Weselek et al., 2021a)

Tuber dry mass	For each sub-plot, a 2-kg sub-sample of harvested tuber is fresh weighed, oven-dried (1 week, 105 °C) and the dry weight is determined to calculate the dry mass.	(Schulz et al., 2019)
----------------	---	-----------------------

3.4. CROP MODELS PARAMETERISATION

Although the crop models implemented in the simulation platform have distinctive characteristics, there are many parameters, especially inherent to crop management and phenology that we will consider common. Table 8 lists the phenological information common to the two crop models (i.e. DAISY, GECROS).

Table 8. Overview of environmental parameters required for parameterisation of crop models Daisy and Gecros.

	Minimum required	Recommended	Comment
Lower boundary condition	Where is the groundwater? Drainage depth and density if present When are the drains running?	Measurement of drain flow Measurement of groundwater level (piezometers) The level and variation in a nearby stream.	Only for Daisy model
Soil profile	Soil horizons in the root zone, For each horizon: Texture, bulk density, OM, and C/N-ratio.	Moisture retention curves and saturated and unsaturated hydraulic conductivity.	Only one horizon for Gecros
Management	Tillage operations: Date, type of operation, working depth		Applicable only for Daisy model
	Sowing: Date, crop, amount of seed applied.		Seed per m2 for Gecrose model
	Fertilization: Date, type and amount applied.	For organic fertilizer, DM%, C% and N% as well as NH4-fraction is useful.	

	Irrigation: On actual experiments, date and amount applied should be specified		Daisy can irrigate according to different rules (e.g. moisture content or suction)
	Harvest: Date, crop, stub height and fraction of the primary and secondary product harvested.		

Table 9 summarizes the key parameters used in the GECROS and Daisy models to simulate light interception and biomass accumulation. Notably, there are significant differences in how these models handle photosynthesis. While Daisy employs a standard light response curve to calculate gross photosynthesis (Abrahamsen and Hansen, 2000), GECROS uses a more complex approach that will be detailed in the next section. The parameters relevant to GECROS, not mentioned in Tables 9 and 10 will also be clarified.

For this project, Daisy simulations will utilize the standard photosynthesis model. This model calculates gross photosynthesis for each crop layer individually, based on a light response curve with two key calibratable parameters: the crop-specific photosynthetic rate at saturated light intensity (F_m) and the corresponding initial light use efficiency at low intensity (Q_{eff}).

Table 9. Information required for calibration of phenology.

	Minimum required	Recommended	Unit/Comment
Sowing date	recorded	More than one year	
Date of emergence	recorded	More than one year	
Weather	recorded		
Date of emergence	recorded	More than one year	
Date of flowering /earing / tuberization		More than one year	
Date of important growth stages between emergence and flowering	recorded		BBCH scale provides an excellent tool to identify intermediate phases
Date of maturity	recorded	More than one year	Based on judgement of when the crop is ready for harvest
Date of harvest	recorded		

Table 10. Parameters relevant to simulate growth

	Minimum required	Recommended	Unit/Comment
Plant height	From literature	Measured under	cm

		Controlled conditions or in the field	
Specific Leaf Area	From literature	The parameter can be estimated from measurements of leaf area and weighing at different growth stages	cm ² /g
Q _{eff}	From literature		[(g CO ₂ /m ² /h)/(W/m ²)]
F _m	From literature		[g CO ₂ /m ² /h]
Reflection coefficient of crop canopy	From literature	Measured under Controlled conditions or in the field	Not calibrated in this project
Extinction coefficient of crop canopy	From literature		Not calibrated in this project

4. BIOGASDONERIGHT ® PROTOCOLS

Biomethane production offers a sustainable and renewable energy source derived from organic waste, such as agricultural residues and animal manure. This versatile biogas can be upgraded to biomethane, a renewable natural gas equivalent that can be used for heating, electricity generation, and as a vehicle fuel. By utilizing waste streams and reducing reliance on fossil fuels, biomethane production contributes to a circular economy and helps mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.

4.1. OBJECTIVES OF THE EXPERIMENTAL TRIALS

The *BiogasDoneRight (BDR)* agricultural protocols proposed in Value4Farm are package of existing and innovative agricultural practices around which farmers, that are upgrading their biogas plant into Biomethane production, can redesign the farm carbon (C) and nutrient cycles and crop rotation in order to: 1) increase primary productivity on the farm by allocating the production of additional carbon on the farm to the anaerobic digestion, 2) realize the above-mentioned production of additional C by contemporary increasing the feed and food production per unit of land and contributing to additional C removals by sequestering carbon in soil and reducing GHG emissions related to crop production. The main objectives of the *BDR* agricultural protocols is to deploy, monitor and verify at field level through farm scale field trials the following three main benefits:

1. nutrients use efficiency (NUE) and circularity (C + NP);
2. increase cumulative yearly yield of food and feedstock for biomethane production and animals;
3. net additional climate co-benefits to anaerobic digestion (as soil C sequestration and/or soil emission reduction at field level).

A 2-y operational crop production protocol will be deployed at two CIB associated farms to monitor and verify through a hybrid sampling+modelling approach the abovementioned benefits at field level. Once the results are verified at field level for their accuracy and scalability, a farm scale scenario adoption of the BDR protocol will be lay out and impacts simulated compared to baseline scenario at whole farm level (land+power plant+stable) to calculate the farm nutrient balance and carbon footprint.

4.2. DESCRIPTION OF EXPERIMENTAL TRIALS

The BDR protocol consists of a combination of an improved crop rotation (e.g. maize, sorghum, winter cereals, soybean) with the application of the 4R Nutrient Stewardship that utilizes fertilizer best management practices addressing the right fertilizer source, at the right rate, the right time, and in the right place. The 4R concept will be expanded to a C + Nutrient Stewardship since digestate will be substituted to mineral fertilization.

The combination of the following agronomic practices characterizes the BDR protocols:

- improved crop rotation (second summer cereal crop, introduction of grain legume and forage cover crops);
- adoption of precision fertilization (right time and right rate) through variable rate technology (VRT) that leverages prescription maps produced with remote and proximal sensing data;
- introduction of combined machineries such as strip tillage, self-propelled machineries for digestate application (right place), combined power/disk harrow sowing machines;
- substitution of mineral fertilizer with digestate (right source) for all crops into rotation according to pedo-climatic conditions of the season.

The adoption of BDR protocols will start in July 2024, following the June harvest of silage winter crops such as winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) or triticale (*x Triticosecale*). These protocols will be implemented on fields with a minimum area of 10 hectares per farm.

The main crop rotation will be the following: second maize/sorghum crop (*Zea mays* L./*Sorghum bicolor* L.) → silage winter crop (*Triticum aestivum* L.) → second soybean crop (*Glycine max* L.) → forage cover crop mixture (Figure 12).

Figure 11. crop rotation tested in the BDR protocol

The field will be split in two parts: in one part the common soil and nutrient management of the farm will be applied while in the second part an advanced innovative management will be adopted. Another series of fields around the trials (same soil type) will be selected to have the baseline scenario for crop rotation.

The machineries for tillage, sowing and fertilisation will be selected among the ones available at local contractors. The prescription maps will be generated using a spatialized soil nutrient balance approach

where the fertiliser inputs are based on delineation of management zones. It will be used as input to calculate nutrient offtake yield maps estimated from satellite while the soil components of the balance will use high resolution soil maps of texture components (sand, silt, clay) and soil organic matter content generated by proximal sensing sensor (Veris iScan). The calculation of fertilization rate will be done on a N-basis and considered the use of digestate with the latest lab-measured N concentration available. If P and K provided with digestate would not meet crop nutrients requirements, an additional mineral fertilization will be applied. Regarding tillage equipment strip tillage will be used on spring or summer second cereal row crops while combined tillage and sowing machines will be used on winter and cover crops. Strip tillage combined with self-propelled machineries will be used to inject digestate at pre sowing in summer/spring cereals or soybean while top dress fertilization of winter crops will be applied only once with the use of nitrogen inhibitor before tillering with self-propelled machineries. Harvest will be done with combined and/or silage harvester equipped with calibrated yield sensor for producing harvest maps. The crop's variety will be selected by farmers according to know-how and practical needs while the mixture of the cover crops species will be composed according to the expected protein content for its forage use and functions to be obtain (organic matter build up, biofumigation, nitrogen catch etc..).

4.3. MONITORING AND VERIFICATION OF *BIOGASDONERIGHT* PROTOCOLS IMPACTS AT FIELD LEVEL

During BDR protocol adoption the following crop, soil and activity data will be collected in BDR field and baseline plots by combining field measurement, soil-crop modelling estimates, remote sensing (RS) estimates and tractor/farm management information systems (FMIS) data on crop inputs:

- A. Crop yield and biomass during growing season (hybrid: RS-based crop modelling + harvest map);
- B. Soil C sequestration (hybrid: smart sampling/lab measurement + soil C modelling);
- C. Soil nutrients stock changes (measurement: smart sampling + lab measurement);
- D. Field N leaching and N₂O emissions (soil-crop modelling);
- E. Carbon and nutrients inputs (FMIS, tractor data and farmer declaration);
- F. Agrochemicals use (FMIS and farmer declaration);
- G. Gasoline and energy consumption (FMIS, tractor data and farmer declaration).

These data are taken to calculate the impact of BDR protocol on the three main benefits mentioned above.

To estimate **cumulative yearly yield**, biomass and crop yield of each crop will be estimated with a simple crop model based on light use efficiency (LUE) theory (Monteith 1972; Dhillion et al., 2020). The model is based on a semi-empiric approach (Dhillion et al., 2020) and calculates the daily aboveground biomass

as a product of the absorbed photosynthetic active radiation (APAR, MJ/m²/day)] and light use efficiency (LUE). It has two fundamental assumptions: (1) Net Primary Production (NPP) is linearly related to APAR, and (2) the actual LUE (ϵ_g) is downregulated from its theoretical maximum LUE (ϵ_0) by environmental conditions, such as temperature or water stress. The NPP estimated here as aboveground biomass (AGB) will be calculated as in Dhillon et al. (2023) by assimilating satellite data to estimate the fraction of PAR absorbed by the canopy (fAPAR). The cumulative AGB during the growing season will be used to estimate yield and a spatial yield map will be produced for each crop annually. Yield estimates will be validated against harvest map and field data collected via manual harvesting in selected 20 x 20 m elementary sampling unit (ESU). On those sample nutrient and C content will be measured to calculate C and nutrient exports. To estimate **climate benefits** of BDR protocols will be used the methodologies and formula proposed by the EU regulation 2022/0394 (COD) establishing a Union Certification framework for carbon removals (CRCF regulation). Two types of benefits will be calculated: **temporary net C removal benefit** and **net soil emissions reduction benefit**. A hybrid sampling+modelling approach will be used to monitor and verify net C removal benefit as soil C sequestration. The approach integrates proximal sensing and remote sensing-based estimate to provide input to Roth-C soil C model.

Figure 12. Monitoring and verification workflow

The BDR protocol shall provide a temporary net carbon removal benefit as stated by Art.4 of the CRCF regulation if temporary net carbon removal benefit is calculated as:

$$CR_{\text{baseline}} - CR_{\text{BDRprotocol}} - GHG_{\text{associated}} > 0 \quad (1)$$

where:

CR_{baseline} is the carbon removal under the baseline scenario (control plots),

$CR_{\text{BDRprotocol}}$ is the total carbon removal of the set of practices adopted with BDR protocols,

$GHG_{associated}$ is the increase in direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions, over the entire lifecycle of the BDR protocols which are due to its implementation, including CO_2 equivalent emissions (CO_2 , N_2O and CH_4) from different field operations (energy use, crop production, soil emission from fertilizer use, fertilizer production, residue management and off-farm transport). The direct and indirect CO_2 emission will be calculated using Cool Farm Tool (CFT) GHG calculator while direct and indirect field N_2O emissions emission will be estimated with DAISY model.

If N_2O soil emission decrease as a result of the BDR protocol adoption that results in temporary carbon removal, they will be quantified, reported and accounted for as **net soil emissions reduction benefit** and calculated as follows:

$$\text{Net soil emission reduction benefit} = CR_{baseline} - CR_{BDRprotocol} + SE_{baseline} - SE_{BDRprotocol} - GHG_{associated} > 0 \quad (2)$$

where $SE_{baseline}$ are the agricultural N_2O soil emissions under the baseline scenario; $SE_{BDRprotocol}$ are the total agricultural soil emissions of the BDR protocol.

Nutrient use efficiency at field level will be calculated for a series of crop N-efficiency parameters and used to calculate AESI, an agro-environmental sustainability index (i.e. product of the dry yield and NUE) proposed by Grillo et al. (2021):

- N use efficiency (NUE; $kg\ kg^{-1}$) as the ratio of grain yield to N supply, where N supply is the sum of soil NO_3^- -N at sowing, mineralized N and N fertilizer;
- N uptake efficiency (NU_pE ; $kg\ kg^{-1}$) as the ratio of total plant N uptake to N supply;
- N utilization efficiency (NU_tE ; $kg\ kg^{-1}$) as the ratio of grain yield to total plant N uptake.

AESI will be calculated to evaluate agronomic performance of the optimized digestate use within BDR protocol.

4.4. SCENARIO ANALYSES OF BDR PROTOCOL ADOPTION AT FARM LEVEL

During BDR protocol application and monitoring at field-level, a farm-gate mass-balance nutrient balance will be done to calculate a set of **farm-level nutrients use efficiency (NUE)** and **circularity indicators**. This is done to identify the entry points where in the farm BDR protocol might be adopted for improving farming performance related to C and nutrients balance. Three main indicators will be calculated: NUE (farm-gate ratio of N outputs to N inputs), N surplus and N output in agricultural products (Quemada et al. 2020). Circularity indicators (van Loon et al., 2023) will also be calculated to check the consistency of the current practices in closing and tightening farm-scale C and nutrient loops (e.g. NPK with C-rich digestate). Once the field data will be validated and their uncertainties estimated, based on the most promising results on climate-, nutrient- and yield-related benefits, with farmers will be designed an scenario analysis to identify

the most impactful BDR protocol to be adopted at farm level. It will be created first a farm-level N input vs. N output diagram and carbon footprint map for the baseline scenario and it will be identified the space to target for maximum N output and upper limit for N surplus and the more cost-efficient climate benefits attainable. The lower and upper limits for NUE (Figure 14) will be set by farm-specific characteristic operating space (COS) as proposed by Quemada et al. (2020). The COS is the working space within which the thresholds of a set of indicators are fulfilled, and thus it can be used to indicate the need for improving farm performance and assess the performance of the BDR protocol scenario adoption. The definition of the COS will consider the actual size of the farm, the biomethane plant and the stable needs in terms of feedstock and digestate production. Based on the identified thresholds, a BDR adoption scenario will be designed, and its impact trajectories will be estimated through an ex-ante simulation experiment. Farm data and model and DAISY crop-soil model will be used to estimate soil and crop data needed to calculate NUE and circularity indicators while Roth-C and CFT will be used to calculate the carbon footprint of the farm.

Figure 13 Ideal pathways for farms to enter the characteristic operating space, based on yield-N input relationships and sustainable intensification strategies (source: Quemada et al., 2020).

5. CONCLUSION

The implementation of agrivoltaic (APV) systems and BiomethaneDoneRight (BDR) protocols in the Mediterranean region offers a promising pathway towards sustainable agriculture. The integration of these technologies aims to enhance crop productivity, optimize resource use, and contribute to climate change mitigation by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and sequestering carbon in soils.

APV systems, which combine crop production with photovoltaic energy generation, demonstrate the potential to improve crop yields and stability, particularly under the challenging climatic conditions typical of the Mediterranean region. By managing light transmittance and creating targeted shading patterns, APV systems can leverage the natural tolerance of certain crops to lower light levels, thus optimizing both crop health and yield. BDR protocols, which include improved crop rotations, precision fertilization, and the use of digestate as a fertilizer, are designed to enhance nutrient use efficiency and circularity. These protocols not only increase the cumulative yearly yield of food and feedstock but also provide significant climate co-benefits by enhancing soil carbon sequestration and reducing emissions.

The combination of APV and BDR within the Value4Farm project showcases the potential for synergistic benefits. APV can meet the energy needs of biomethane plants, while crops suitable for biogas conversion can be cultivated alongside traditional cash crops. This integrated approach maximizes land use efficiency, maintains food production, and enhances the overall sustainability of agricultural practices. The adoption of APV systems and BDR protocols represents a viable strategy for improving agricultural resilience and sustainability in the Mediterranean region. Future research and field trials will be crucial in refining these technologies, ensuring their scalability, and maximizing their benefits for farmers and the environment.

6. REFERENCES

- Abrahamsen, P., Hansen, S., 2000. Daisy: an open soil-crop-atmosphere system model. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 15, 313-330. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152\(00\)00003-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1364-8152(00)00003-7)
- Ahmed, M.S., Khan, M. Rezwan, Haque, A., Khan, M. Ryan, 2022. Agrivoltaics analysis in a techno-economic framework: Understanding why agrivoltaics on rice will always be profitable. *Applied Energy* 323, 119560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119560>
- Al Mamun, M.A., Garba, I.I., Campbell, S., Dargusch, P., deVoil, P., Aziz, A.A., 2023. Biomass production of a sub-tropical grass under different photovoltaic installations using different grazing strategies. *Agricultural Systems* 208, 103662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103662>
- Amaducci, S., Yin, X., Colauzzi, M., 2018. Agrivoltaic systems to optimise land use for electric energy production. *Applied Energy* 220, 545-561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.03.081>
- Arenas-Corraliza, M.G., López-Díaz, M.L., Rolo, V., Moreno, G., 2021. Wheat and barley cultivars show plant traits acclimation and increase grain yield under simulated shade in Mediterranean conditions. *J Agronomy Crop Science* 207, 100-119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jac.12465>
- Artru, S., Garré, S., Dupraz, C., Hiel, M.-P., Blitz-Frayret, C., Lassois, L., 2017. Impact of spatio-temporal shade dynamics on wheat growth and yield, perspectives for temperate agroforestry. *European Journal of Agronomy* 82, 60-70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2016.10.004>
- Asseng, S., Zhu, Y., Basso, B., Wilson, T., Cammarano, D., 2014. Simulation Modeling: Applications in Cropping Systems, in: *Encyclopedia of Agriculture and Food Systems*. Elsevier, pp. 102-112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-52512-3.00233-3>
- Bannayan M., Hoogenboom G., Crout NMJ. 2004. Photothermal impact on maize performance: a simulation approach. *Ecological Modelling*, 180, 2-3, p. 277-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2004.04.022>
- Barron-Gafford, G.A., Pavao-Zuckerman, M.A., Minor, R.L., Sutter, L.F., Barnett-Moreno, I., Blackett, D.T., Thompson, M., Dimond, K., Gerlak, A.K., Nabhan, G.P., Macknick, J.E., 2019. Agrivoltaics provide mutual benefits across the food-energy-water nexus in drylands. *Nature Sustainability* 2, 848-855. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0364-5>
- Beed, F.D., Paveley, N.D., Sylvester-Bradley, R., 2007. Predictability of wheat growth and yield in light-limited conditions. *J. Agric. Sci.* 145, 63-79. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859606006678>
- Benedetti, M., Vecchi, V., Barera, S., Dall'Osto, L., 2018. Biomass from microalgae: the potential of domestication towards sustainable biofactories. *Microb Cell Fact* 17, 173. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-018-1019-3>
- Bonfante, A., Terribile, F., & Bouma, J. 2019. Refining physical aspects of soil quality and soil health when exploring the effects of soil degradation and climate change on biomass production: an Italian case study. *SOIL*, 5(1), 1-14.
- Brisson, N., Gary, C., Justes, E., Roche, R., Mary, B., Ripoche, D., Zimmer, D., Sierra, J., Bertuzzi, P., Burger, P., Bussire, F., Cabidoche, Y.M., Cellier, P., Debaeke, P., Gaudillre, J.P., Hnault, C., Maraux,

- F., Seguin, B., Sinoquet, H., 2003. An overview of the crop model stics. *European Journal of Agronomy* 18, 309-332. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301\(02\)00110-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(02)00110-7)
- Campana, P.E., Stridh, B., Amaducci, S., Colauzzi, M., 2021. Optimisation of vertically mounted agrivoltaic systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129091>
- Cooper, M., Messina, C. D., Podlich, D., et al. 2014. Predicting the future of plant breeding: complementing empirical evaluation with genetic prediction. *Crop and Pasture Science*, 65(4), 311.
- Cox, W.J., 1996. Whole-Plant Physiological and Yield Responses of Maize to Plant Density. *Agronomy Journal* 88, 489-496. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj1996.00021962008800030022x>
- Dal Prà, A., Miglietta, F., Genesio, L., Lanini, G.M., Bozzi, R., Morè, N., Greco, A., Fabbri, M.C., 2024. Determination of feed yield and quality parameters of whole crop durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) biomass under agrivoltaic system. *Agroforest Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-024-00979-8>
- Dhillon MS, Dahms T, Kuebert-Flock C, Borg E, Conrad C, Ullmann T. Modelling Crop Biomass from Synthetic Remote Sensing Time Series: Example for the DEMMIN Test Site, Germany. *Remote Sensing*. 2020; 12(11):1819. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12111819>
- Dhillon MS, Kübert-Flock C, Dahms T, Rummler T, Arnault J, Steffan-Dewenter I, Ullmann T. Evaluation of MODIS, Landsat 8 and Sentinel-2 Data for Accurate Crop Yield Predictions: A Case Study Using STARFM NDVI in Bavaria, Germany. *Remote Sensing*. 2023; 15(7):1830. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15071830>
- Dos Santos Neto, A., Panozzo, A., Piotto, S., Mezzalira, G., Furlan, L., Vamerali, T., 2024. Screening old and modern wheat varieties for shading tolerance within a specialized poplar plantation for agroforestry farming systems implementation. *Agroforest Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-024-00956-1>
- Dufour, L., Metay, A., Talbot, G., Dupraz, C., 2013. Assessing Light Competition for Cereal Production in Temperate Agroforestry Systems using Experimentation and Crop Modelling. *J Agronomy Crop Science* 199, 217-227. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jac.12008>
- Dupraz, C., 2023. Assessment of the ground coverage ratio of agrivoltaic systems as a proxy for potential crop productivity. *Agroforest Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-023-00906-3>
- Dupraz, C., Marrou, H., Talbot, G., Dufour, L., Nogier, A., Ferard, Y., 2011. Combining solar photovoltaic panels and food crops for optimising land use: Towards new agrivoltaic schemes. *Renewable Energy* 36, 2725-2732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2011.03.005>
- Echarte, L., Luque, S., Andrade, F.H., Sadras, V.O., Cirilo, A., Otegui, M.E., Vega, C.R.C., 2000. Response of maize kernel number to plant density in Argentinean hybrids released between 1965 and 1993. *Field Crops Research* 68, 1-8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4290\(00\)00101-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4290(00)00101-5)
- Edouard, S., Combes, D., Iseghem, M.V., Tin, M.N.W., Escobar-Gutiérrez, A.J., 2023. Increasing land productivity with agriphotovoltaics: Application to an alfalfa field. *Applied Energy* 329, 120207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120207>
- Fan, Y., Chen, J., Wang, Z., Tan, T., Li, S., Li, J., Wang, B., Zhang, J., Cheng, Y., Wu, X., Yang, W., Yang, F., 2019. Soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merr.) seedlings response to shading: leaf structure, photosynthesis and proteomic analysis. *BMC Plant Biol* 19, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12870-019-1633-1>

- Ferrara, G., Boselli, M., Palasciano, M., Mazzeo, A., 2023. Effect of shading determined by photovoltaic panels installed above the vines on the performance of cv. Corvina (*Vitis vinifera* L.). *Scientia Horticulturae* 308, 111595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2022.111595>
- Franklin, K.A., 2008. Shade avoidance. *New Phytologist* 179, 930-944. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2008.02507.x>
- Gao, J., Shi, J., Dong, S., Liu, P., Zhao, B., Zhang, J., 2017. Grain yield and root characteristics of summer maize (*Zea mays* L.) under shade stress conditions. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science* 203, 562-573. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jac.12210>
- Gommers, C.M.M., Visser, E.J.W., Onge, K.R.S., Voeselek, L.A.C.J., Pierik, R., 2013. Shade tolerance: when growing tall is not an option. *Trends in Plant Science* 18, 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2012.09.008>
- Grillo, F., Piccoli, I., Furlanetto, I., Ragazzi, F., Obber, S., Bonato, T., ... & Morari, F. (2021). Agro-environmental sustainability of anaerobic digestate fractions in intensive cropping systems: insights regarding the nitrogen use efficiency and crop performance. *Agronomy*, 11(4), 745.
- Grubbs, E.K., Gruss, S.M., Schull, V.Z., Gosney, M.J., Mickelbart, M.V., Brouder, S., Gitau, M.W., Bermel, P., Tuinstra, M.R., Agrawal, R., 2024. Optimized agrivoltaic tracking for nearly-full commodity crop and energy production. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 191, 114018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114018>
- Jiang, S., Tang, D., Zhao, L., Liang, C., Cui, N., Gong, D., Wang, Y., Feng, Y., Hu, X., Peng, Y., 2022. Effects of different photovoltaic shading levels on kiwifruit growth, yield and water productivity under “agrivoltaic” system in Southwest China. *Agricultural Water Management* 269, 107675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107675>
- Jo, H., Asekova, S., Bayat, M.A., Ali, L., Song, J.T., Ha, Y.-S., Hong, D.-H., Lee, J.-D., 2022. Comparison of Yield and Yield Components of Several Crops Grown under Agro-Photovoltaic System in Korea. *Agriculture* 12, 619. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12050619>
- Juillion, P., Lopez, G., Fumey, D., Lesniak, V., Génard, M., Vercambre, G., 2022. Shading apple trees with an agrivoltaic system: Impact on water relations, leaf morphophysiological characteristics and yield determinants. *Scientia Horticulturae* 306, 111434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2022.111434>
- Kacheyo, O.C., van Dijk, L.C.M., de Vries, M.E., Struik, P.C., 2021. Augmented descriptions of growth and development stages of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) grown from different types of planting material. *Annals of Applied Biology* 178, 549-566. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aab.12661>
- Katsikogiannis, O.A., Ziar, H., Isabella, O., 2022. Integration of bifacial photovoltaics in agrivoltaic systems: A synergistic design approach. *Applied Energy* 309, 118475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2021.118475>
- Kawano, K., 1990. Harvest index and evolution of major food crop cultivars in the tropics. *Euphytica* 46, 195-202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00027218>
- Kim, Sojung, Kim, Sumin, Yoon, C.-Y., 2021. An Efficient Structure of an Agrophotovoltaic System in a Temperate Climate Region. *Agronomy* 11, 1584. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11081584>

- Ko, J., Cho, J., Choi, J., Yoon, C.-Y., An, K.-N., Ban, J.-O., Kim, D.-K., 2021. Simulation of Crop Yields Grown under Agro-Photovoltaic Panels: A Case Study in Chonnam Province, South Korea. *Energies* 14, 8463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14248463>
- Kuruppuarachchi, D.S.P., 1990. Intercropped potato (*Solanum* spp.): Effect of shade on growth and tuber yield in the northwestern regosol belt of Sri Lanka. *Field Crops Research, Intercropping of the Potato in the Tropics* 25, 61-72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290\(90\)90072-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290(90)90072-J)
- Laub, M., Pataczek, L., Feuerbacher, A., Zikeli, S., Högy, P., 2022. Contrasting yield responses at varying levels of shade suggest different suitability of crops for dual land-use systems: a meta-analysis. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 42, 51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-022-00783-7>
- Lázaro, L., Abbate, P.E., Cogliatti, D.H., Andrade, F.H., 2010. Relationship between yield, growth and spike weight in wheat under phosphorus deficiency and shading. *J. Agric. Sci.* 148, 83-93. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859609990402>
- Lee, H.J., Park, H.H., Kim, Y.O., Kuk, Y.I., 2022. Crop Cultivation Underneath Agro-Photovoltaic Systems and Its Effects on Crop Growth, Yield, and Photosynthetic Efficiency. *Agronomy* 12, 1842. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12081842>
- Li, H., Jiang, D., Wollenweber, B., Dai, T., Cao, W., 2010. Effects of shading on morphology, physiology and grain yield of winter wheat. *European Journal of Agronomy* 33, 267-275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EJA.2010.07.002>
- Li, Y., He, N., Hou, J., Xu, L., Liu, C., Zhang, J., Wang, Q., Zhang, X., Wu, X., 2018. Factors Influencing Leaf Chlorophyll Content in Natural Forests at the Biome Scale. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 6, 64. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2018.00064>
- Lu, S.M., Zainali, S., Stridh, B., Avelin, A., Amaducci, S., Colauzzi, M., Campana, P.E., 2022. Photosynthetically active radiation decomposition models for agrivoltaic systems applications. *Solar Energy* 244, 536-549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2022.05.046>
- Maddonni, G.A., Otegui, M.E., Bonhomme, R., 1998. Grain yield components in maize: II. Postsilking growth and kernel weight. *Field Crops Research* 56, 257-264. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4290\(97\)00094-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4290(97)00094-4)
- Marrou, H., Guilioni, L., Dufour, L., Dupraz, C., Wery, J., 2013a. Microclimate under agrivoltaic systems: Is crop growth rate affected in the partial shade of solar panels? *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 177, 117-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2013.04.012>
- Marrou, H., Wery, J., Dufour, L., Dupraz, C., 2013b. Productivity and radiation use efficiency of lettuces grown in the partial shade of photovoltaic panels. *European Journal of Agronomy* 44, 54-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EJA.2012.08.003>
- Meier U. 2001. Growth stages of mono- and dicotyledonous plants. *BBCH Monograph*. <https://doi:10.5073/bbch0515>
- Meier, U., Bleiholder, H., Buhr, L., Feller, C., Hack, H., Heß, M., Lancashire, P.D., Schnock, U., Stauß, R., Van Den Boom, T., Weber, E., Zwerger, P., 2009. The BBCH system to coding the phenological growth stages of plants - history and publications -. *Journal of Cultivated Plants* 41-52 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.5073/JFK.2009.02.01>

- Midmore, D.J., 1984. Potato (*Solanum* spp.) in the hot tropics I. Soil temperature effects on emergence, plant development and yield. *Field Crops Research* 8, 255-271. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290\(84\)90073-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290(84)90073-X)
- Midmore, D.J., Roca, J., Berrios, D., 1988. Potato (*Solanum* spp.) in the hot tropics IV. Intercropping with maize and the influence of shade on potato microenvironment and crop growth. *Field Crops Research* 18, 141-157. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290\(88\)90005-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4290(88)90005-6)
- Mu, H., Jiang, D., Wollenweber, B., Dai, T., Jing, Q., Cao, W., 2010. Long-term Low Radiation Decreases Leaf Photosynthesis, Photochemical Efficiency and Grain Yield in Winter Wheat. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science* 196, 38-47. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-037X.2009.00394.x>
- Munger, P., Bleiholder, H., Hack, H., Hess, M., Stauss, R., van den Boom, T., Weber, E., 1997. Phenological Growth Stages of the Soybean Plant (*Glycine max* L. MERR.): Codification and Description According to the BBCH Scale*. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science* 179, 209-217. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-037X.1997.tb00519.x>
- Niinemets, Ü., Valladares, F., 2004. Photosynthetic Acclimation to Simultaneous and Interacting Environmental Stresses Along Natural Light Gradients: Optimality and Constraints. *Plant Biology* 6, 254-268. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2004-817881>
- Pataczek, L., Weselek, A., Bauerle, A., Högy, P., Lewandowski, I., Zikeli, S., Schweiger, A., 2023. Agrivoltaics mitigate drought effects in winter wheat. *Physiologia Plantarum* 175, e14081. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.14081>
- Peers, G., Truong, T.B., Ostendorf, E., Busch, A., Elrad, D., Grossman, A.R., Hippler, M., Niyogi, K.K., 2009. An ancient light-harvesting protein is critical for the regulation of algal photosynthesis. *Nature* 462, 518-521. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08587>
- Poonia, S., Jat, N.K., Santra, P., Singh, A.K., Jain, D., Meena, H.M., 2022. Techno-economic evaluation of different agri-voltaic designs for the hot arid ecosystem India. *Renewable Energy* 184, 149-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.11.074>
- Poorter, H., Niinemets, Ü., Poorter, L., Wright, I.J., Villar, R., 2009. Causes and consequences of variation in leaf mass per area (LMA): a meta-analysis. *New Phytologist* 182, 565-588. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2009.02830.x>
- Potenza, E., Croci, M., Colauzzi, M., Amaducci, S., 2022. Agrivoltaic System and Modelling Simulation: A Case Study of Soybean (*Glycine max* L.) in Italy. *Horticulturae* 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae8121160>
- Prà, A.D., Genesio, L., Carotenuto, F., Baronti, S., Moriondo, M., Greco, A., Morè, N., Reboldi, A., 2023. Salad yields under Agrivoltaics: a field test.
- Prakash, V., Lunagaria, M.M., Trivedi, A.P., Upadhyaya, A., Kumar, R., Das, A., Kumar Gupta, A., Kumar, Y., 2023. Shading and PAR under different density agrivoltaic systems, their simulation and effect on wheat productivity. *European Journal of Agronomy* 149, 126922. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2023.126922>

Quemada, M., Lassaletta, L., Jensen, L. S., Godinot, O., Brentrup, F., Buckley, C., ... & Oenema, O. (2020). Exploring nitrogen indicators of farm performance among farm types across several European case studies. *Agricultural Systems*, 177, 102689.

Ramos-Fuentes I.A., Elamri Y., Cheviron B., Dejean C., Belaud G., Fumey D. 2003. Effects of shade and deficit irrigation on maize growth and development in fixed and dynamic AgriVoltaic systems, *Agricultural Water Management*, Volume 280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108187>.

Ramos-Fuentes, I.A., Elamri, Y., Cheviron, B., Dejean, C., Belaud, G., Fumey, D., 2023. Effects of shade and deficit irrigation on maize growth and development in fixed and dynamic AgriVoltaic systems. *Agricultural Water Management* 280. <https://doi.org/bologna@dottorato.it>

Reeza, A.A., Noor, N.F.M., Ahmed, O.H., Masuri, M.A., 2024. Shading Effect of Photovoltaic Panels on Growth of Selected Tropical Vegetable Crops. *Scientia Horticulturae* 324, 112574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2023.112574>

Reher, T., Lavaert, C., Willockx, B., Huyghe, Y., Bisschop, J., Martens, J.A., Diels, J., Cappelle, J., Van De Poel, B., 2024. Potential of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) production in vertical bifacial, tracked, or elevated agrivoltaic systems in Belgium. *Applied Energy* 359, 122679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122679>

Santra P, Mohan Meena H., Yadav O.P. 2021. Spatial and temporal variation of photosynthetic photon flux density within agrivoltaic system in hot arid region of India, *Biosystems Engineering*, 209, p. 74-93, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.06.017>.

Sarr A., Soro Y.M., Tossa A.K., Diop L. 2024. A new approach for modelling photovoltaic panel configuration maximizing crop yield and photovoltaic array outputs in agrivoltaics systems, *Energy Conversion and Management*, 309, 118436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118436>

Schindele, S., Trommsdorff, M., Schlaak, A., Oberfell, T., Bopp, G., Reise, C., Braun, C., Weselek, A., Bauerle, A., Högy, P., Goetzberger, A., Weber, E., 2020. Implementation of agrophotovoltaics: Techno-economic analysis of the price-performance ratio and its policy implications. *Applied Energy* 265, 114737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114737>

Schoving C., Stöckle CO., Colombet C., Champolivier L., Debaeke P. and Maury P. 2020. Combining Simple Phenotyping and Photothermal Algorithm for the Prediction of Soybean Phenology: Application to a Range of Common Cultivars Grown in Europe. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10:1755. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.01755

Schulz, V.S., Munz, S., Stolzenburg, K., Hartung, J., Weisenburger, S., Graeff-Hönninger, S., 2019. Impact of Different Shading Levels on Growth, Yield and Quality of Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). *Agronomy* 9, 330. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9060330>

Schweiger, A.H., Pataczek, L., 2023. How to reconcile renewable energy and agricultural production in a drying world. *Plants People Planet* ppp3.10371. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp3.10371>

Sekiyama, T., Nagashima, A., 2019. Solar sharing for both food and clean energy production: Performance of agrivoltaic systems for corn, a typical shade-intolerant crop. *Environments - MDPI* 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments6060065>

Semeraro, T., Scarano, A., Curci, L.M., Leggieri, A., Lenucci, M., Basset, A., Santino, A., Piro, G., De Caroli, M., 2024. Shading effects in agrivoltaic systems can make the difference in boosting food security in climate change. *Applied Energy* 358, 122565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122565>

- Thorp, K. R., DeJonge, K. C., Kaleita, A. L., et al. 2008. Methodology for the use of DSSAT models for precision agriculture decision support. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 64(2), 276-285.
- Tokatlidis, I.S., Has, V., Melidis, V., Has, I., Mylonas, I., Evgenidis, G., Copandean, A., Ninou, E., Fasoula, V.A., 2011. Maize hybrids less dependent on high plant densities improve resource-use efficiency in rainfed and irrigated conditions. *Field Crops Research* 120, 345-351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2010.11.006>
- Tripathy, B.C., Oelmüller, R., 2012. Reactive oxygen species generation and signaling in plants. *Plant Signaling & Behavior* 7, 1621-1633. <https://doi.org/10.4161/psb.22455>
- Trommsdorff, M., Kang, J., Reise, C., Schindele, S., Bopp, G., Ehmann, A., Weselek, A., Högy, P., Obergfell, T., 2021. Combining food and energy production: Design of an agrivoltaic system applied in arable and vegetable farming in Germany. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110694>
- Uddling, J., Gelang-Alfredsson, J., Piikki, K., Pleijel, H., 2007. Evaluating the relationship between leaf chlorophyll concentration and SPAD-502 chlorophyll meter readings. *Photosynth Res* 91, 37-46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11120-006-9077-5>
- van Loon, M. P., Vonk, W. J., Hijbeek, R., van Ittersum, M. K., & ten Berge, H. F. (2023). Circularity indicators and their relation with nutrient use efficiency in agriculture and food systems. *Agricultural Systems*, 207, 103610
- Wan, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhang, M., Hong, A., Yang, H., Liu, Y., 2020. Shade effects on growth, photosynthesis and chlorophyll fluorescence parameters of three *Paeonia* species. *PeerJ* 8, e9316. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9316>
- Weselek, A., Bauerle, A., Hartung, J., Zikeli, S., Lewandowski, I., Högy, P., 2021a. Agrivoltaic system impacts on microclimate and yield of different crops within an organic crop rotation in a temperate climate. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 41, 59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00714-y>
- Weselek, A., Bauerle, A., Zikeli, S., Lewandowski, I., Högy, P., 2021b. Effects on Crop Development, Yields and Chemical Composition of Celeriac (*Apium graveolens* L. var. *rapaceum*) Cultivated Underneath an Agrivoltaic System. *Agronomy* 11, 733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11040733>
- Willockx, B., Lavaert, C., Cappelle, J., 2023. Performance evaluation of vertical bifacial and single-axis tracked agrivoltaic systems on arable land. *Renewable Energy* 217, 119181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119181>
- Yin, X. and Van Laar, H., 2005. *Crop Systems Dynamics: An Ecophysiological Simulation Model for Genotype-by-environment Interactions*. Wageningen Academic Pub.
- Yin, X., Laar, H.H. van, 2005. *Crop Systems Dynamics*. Wageningen Academic Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.3920/978-90-8686-539-0>
- Yuan, L., Tang, J., Wang, X., Li, C., 2012. QTL Analysis of Shading Sensitive Related Traits in Maize under Two Shading Treatments. *PLOS ONE* 7, e38696. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0038696>
- Zainali S., Ma Lu S., Stridh B., Avelin A., Amaducci S., Colauzzi M., Campana P.E. 2023. Direct and diffuse shading factors modelling for the most representative agrivoltaic system layouts. *Applied Energy*, 339, 120981, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.120981>

Zhu, X.-G., Long, S.P., Ort, D.R., 2008. What is the maximum efficiency with which photosynthesis can convert solar energy into biomass? *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* 19, 153-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2008.02.004>

